

I-CISK
HUMAN CENTRED CLIMATE SERVICES

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Theory of change and impact of climate services co-creation
across the I- CISK Living Labs

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Innovating Climate services through Integrating Scientific and local Knowledge

Deliverable Title: Theory of change and impact of climate services co-creation across the I-CISK Living Labs

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Executive Summary

Understanding and demonstrating impact is central to the I-CISK project's mission to improve climate services through the integration of local and scientific knowledge. This deliverable presents the approach, process, and progress made in developing a robust framework for monitoring and evaluating impact across the project, with a particular focus on the Theory of Change (ToC) methodology.

I-CISK operates through seven Living Labs (LL) in Europe and beyond, co-creating actionable, user-driven climate services to support local communities and sectors in adapting to climate change. An overarching ToC was first developed to provide strategic coherence across work packages, followed by LL-specific ToC frameworks that contextualise the change pathways in each location. These frameworks map the progression from project inputs and activities to outputs, outcomes, and long-term impacts, while making explicit the assumptions and external factors influencing success.

The development of LL-specific ToCs was carried out through participatory workshops, internal collaboration, and iterative refinement. The process ultimately fostered ownership, increased usability, and enhanced the relevance of ToCs as tools for both planning and adaptive management. The ToCs serve not only to articulate the intended impacts of co-created climate services but also to guide critical reflection and inform mid-course adjustments.

To support systematic monitoring, a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) were designed and aligned with the ToC components. These KPIs were regularly assessed using a traffic-light system to track progress and identify implementation challenges. Complementing the KPIs monitoring, impact stories were collected to capture emerging changes in behaviour, decision-making, institutional practices, and resilience of multiple actors to the climatic hazards (e.g., droughts, floods, and heatwaves).

While validation of assumptions linked to short-term outputs has shown promising results in several LLs, the evaluation of longer-term outcomes and systemic impacts remains an ongoing activity. Continued monitoring and stakeholder engagement will be essential for drawing more definitive conclusions on the sustained value of I-CISK's climate services.

This deliverable outlines the methodology used, presents the overarching and LL-specific ToCs, provides an update on KPI performance and qualitative impact evidence, and reflects on lessons learned to date. The report underscores the role of ToC as a critical asset in ensuring that I-CISK remains impact-focused, user-centred, and adaptive throughout its implementation. The novel approaches and insights documented in this report could be very helpful to co-design, implement, and learn from the embedding of ToC and impact assessment into the course of climate services projects.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	5
2	Methodology.....	6
3	Theory of Change frameworks for the I-CISK project	11
3.1	Overarching Theory of Change.....	11
3.1.1	Co-creation process	11
3.1.2	Inputs	11
3.1.3	Activities	11
3.1.4	Outputs	11
3.1.5	Outcomes.....	12
3.1.6	Impacts	12
3.2	LL-tailored Theory of Change frameworks	14
3.2.1	Rijnland Delta, The Netherlands	14
3.2.2	Andalucía, Spain.....	17
3.2.3	Emilia Romagna, Italy.....	22
3.2.4	Erzsébetváros, Budapest, Hungary.....	25
3.2.5	Crete, Greece	29
3.2.6	Alazani river basin, Georgia.....	33
3.2.7	Southern Lowlands Districts, Lesotho	37
4	Impact monitoring and assessment	40
4.1	Key Performance Indicators	40
4.2	Impact stories	41
5	Measures to maximise the impact of the project: communication and dissemination.....	47
6	Discussion and conclusion	51
7	References.....	53
8	Annexes	56
8.1	Annex-1: An overview of the KPIs, links to the Theory of Change components and co-creation process and their status by M45 (July 2025).	56
8.2	Annex 2: Glossary.....	74

List of Figures

Figure 1: The geographical location of I-CISK's Living Labs in Europe and Africa.	6
Figure 2: The co-creation process and its evaluation criteria to deliver user-centred climate services.	9
Figure 3: Overarching Theory of Change diagram for the ICISK project.	13
Figure 4: Theory of Change diagram tailored to the Rijnland Living Lab.	16
Figure 5: Theory of Change diagram tailored to the Spanish Living Lab.	21
Figure 6: Theory of Change diagram tailored to the Emilia Romagna Living Lab.	24
Figure 7: Theory of Change diagram tailored to the Budapest Living Lab.	28
Figure 8: Theory of Change diagram tailored to the Crete Living Lab.	32
Figure 9: Theory of Change diagram tailored to the Alazani Living Lab.	36
Figure 10: Theory of Change diagram tailored to the Lesotho Living Lab.	39
Figure 11: Framework that integrates Theory of Change elements and KPIs with co-creation process.	73

List of Tables

Table 1: Summary of selected characteristics of the I-CISK Living Labs.....	7
Table 2: An overview of the impact-related KPIs and their status as per M45, July 2025.	40
Table 3: Communication and dissemination related KPIs and their status.....	47
Table 4: An overview of the KPIs and their status as per M45, July 2025.....	56

1 Introduction

Measuring the impact of a project is essential for understanding how its activities contribute to meaningful and lasting change. This was considered especially important in the I-CISK project funded through European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. Working across seven LLs in Europe and beyond, I-CISK aims to support vulnerable communities and sectors in better anticipating, preparing for, and adapting to climate change (I-CISK, *Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge.*, 2021; Masih, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2022). The project focuses not only on producing climate data and tools but also on ensuring that these services are user-driven, actionable, and tailored to the specific needs and contexts of end-users. Assessing impact helps determine whether these efforts translate into concrete benefits, for example, by contributing to enabling informed decision-making, supporting behavioural change, empowering citizen and decision-makers or reducing vulnerability of societies and ecosystems to climate risks. Driving a positive change on these impact areas, among others, is a core focus on many climate-related policies and strategies of the European Union (EU) (European Commission, *Forging a climate-resilient Europe - the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change*, 2021; European Commission, *European Water Resilience Strategy*, 2025).

Embedding a ToC within the framework of policies, plans and projects can support designing and implementing impact-oriented programmes. As such, the ToC and impact assessment were integrated into the design and implementation of the I-CISK project. The ToC provides a structured framework that maps how project inputs, activities and outputs are expected to lead to outcomes and longer-term impacts. It makes visible the assumptions underpinning these pathways and helps identify external factors that may enable or hinder progress (Davies & al., 2018; Katarzyna & Cees, 2021). The ToC in I-CISK has been developed in close connection with the LLs to reflect the specific contexts, priorities, and challenges where the project's innovative Climate Services (CSs) were co-created and used to a varying degree. The ToC also serves as a foundation for learning and adaptive management as the project evolves.

Alongside the ToC, KPIs are crucial to monitor progress systematically and assess whether activities are on track to achieve their intended results. These KPIs provide measurable benchmarks for outputs, outcomes, and, where possible, impacts. Furthermore, evidence of change can be captured through impact stories, highlighting how co-created CSs are used in practice and what difference these make in the lives of users and the sustainable use of natural resources and ecosystems.

Together, the ToC, KPIs, and impact stories form a comprehensive framework for understanding, demonstrating, and communicating the added value of a project. The I-CISK project has incorporated these elements right from the inception. Under work package 1 (WP1), seven LLs are established in the Netherlands, Spain, Italy, Hungary, Greece, Georgia, and Lesotho (Masih, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2022). One of the core objectives of WP1 is to evaluate and monitor the short, medium, and long-term impacts in each of these seven LLs. These are central to achieving the I-CISK impact, serving as key implementation spaces. However, the impact of I-CISK is not limited to the LLs. Other overarching work packages and tasks, such as the co-creation framework and innovative visualisation practices, also have the potential to generate impact in wider contexts and be adopted by global organisations. This report aims to document the progress made on the task dedicated to developing a systematic monitoring and evaluation of the project impacts underpinned by the ToC approach.

2 Methodology

The LL approach is central to the concept and methodology of the I-CISK project in realizing its objectives and impacts. The I-CISK work has been conducted in the seven LLs in Europe and beyond (Figure 1). The LLs are located in diverse geographical and climatic regions facing various climate and water related hazards that impact multiple sectors of the economy in these regions (Table 1). Seven Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs) have been established in the I-CISK LLs (one per LL), which bring together over 150 actors voluntarily contributing to the process of co-creation of pre-operational CSs relevant to their needs and contexts. The MAPs are composed of diverse group of actors well represent policy makers, academia and research, industry and business community, and citizens, alongside actors representing the whole value chain of CS development (e.g. providers, purveyors, and end-users). The inclusion of the MAPs provides a collaborative learning and innovative environment to facilitate co-creation and demonstration of next generation of CSs tailored to the users' needs for improved decision-making at a different spatial and temporal scales across a variety of geographical, climatic, and sectoral conditions in the selected EU regions and beyond.

Figure 1: The geographical location of I-CISK's Living Labs in Europe and Africa.

Table 1: Summary of selected characteristics of the I-CISK Living Labs.

Adapted from (Moschini, Emerton, & al, 2022; Masih, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2022; Egan, Emerton, & al., 2025).

Living Lab	Climate information Köppen classification with mean annual precipitation in mm and temperature in °C (and monthly range)	Main Hazards in focus under I-CISK	Main sectors in focus under I-CISK	CSs currently in use	CSs identified	needs	How the new CSs co-created under I-CISK address the identified needs
Rijnland Delta, the Netherlands	Marine West Coast (Cfb) P: 825 (40-90) T: 11 (4-18)	Drought, water scarcity	Water management, Tourism and water recreation, Agriculture,	Drought monitoring system (including medium-range forecasts), streamflow predictions	Longer lead times; stakeholder engagement; user-friendly visualisation		Developed streamflow forecasts with sub-seasonal to seasonal outlooks; thresholds and historical context integrated; simplified interface to aid water management and policy coordination.
Andalucía, Spain	Mediterranean (Csa) P: 485 (2-70) T: 17 (9-26)	Drought, water scarcity, heatwaves, wildfire	Water management, environment including forestry, agriculture, livestock, tourism, and recreation	reservoir management support, seasonal forecasts, climate projections, climate scenarios viewer, drought monitoring, river basin monitoring	Sector-specific forecasts (rainfall, temperature); improved temporal and spatial resolution		Using map-based and interactive visualisations, provided (1) sub-seasonal to seasonal predictions, (2) 10-year projections; and (3) historical P and T data; (4) agroclimatic indicators; and (5) improved hydrogeological characterization. CS tailored to drought response with improved lead time, spatial resolution, and accessibility.
Emilia-Romagna, Italy	Humid subtropical (Cfa) P: 800 (45-100) T: 13 (2-23)	Drought, water scarcity, floods, and highly variable water supply	Water management, agriculture, environment, energy	Regional climate projections, agriculture water demand forecasts	River discharge forecasts; local data integration; intuitive uncertainty displays		Delivered streamflow forecasts at daily and monthly timescales with colour-coded thresholds; local stakeholder sites integrated; visual simplification of probabilistic outputs.

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Erzsébetv áros, Budapest, Hungary	Humid Continental (Dfb) P: 570 (30-70) T: 11 (-1 to 22)	Heatwaves, Urban heat islands	Tourism and recreation, Health	CLMS Urban Atlas, historical global land surface temperature, meteorological data, air quality monitoring	Urban heat mapping; health-impact fore- casting; greening strategy support	Built high-resolution thermal maps and vegetation overlays; enabled identifica- tion of heat hotspots and monitoring greening efforts; interface tailored for policy and public communication.
Crete, Greece	Mediterranean (CSa) P: 655 (0-140) T: 18 (11-26)	Drought, water scarcity, floods	Tourism and recreation, water management, energy, agriculture	Weather forecasts, climate change impact assessments and vulnerability analysis, hindcasts, short-term forecast service for reservoirs	Tourism indicators; cross-sector forecast- ing; clarity and acces- sibility	Created dashboard of 12 user-defined in- dicators across water, transport infra- structure, and tourism; scenario-based outputs with spatial interactivity and sim- plified charts; users helped define layout. Seasonal forecasting supports operational decision making. Indicator values up to end-of-century support long-term plan- ning.
Alazani river basin, Georgia	Humid subtropical (Cfa) P: 730 (30-106) T: 10 (-3 to 22)	Flood, drought, water scarcity	Water management, agriculture, environment, energy, tourism, and recreation	meteorological and hydrological forecasts, extreme event warnings, agrometeorological bulletins, frost early warning, seasonal outlooks, climate projections	Streamflow predic- tions; early warning; locally adapted ser- vices	Designed river forecast portal with proba- bilistic shading and percentile views; in- cluded observed data and educational tools (e.g. serious game); user training and iterative feedback loop included.
Southern Lowlands Districts, Lesotho	Temperate with Alpine influence (Cfb) P: 700 (10-120) T: 14 (8 to 19)	Drought, water scarcity, cold waves, hailstorms	Disaster management, Agriculture and livestock, humanitarian	Seasonal climate outlook, seasonal meteorological outlook, seasonal hydrological outlook, socio- economic outlook, crop monitoring, vulnerability Assessment	District-level fore- casts; centralised platform; trigger- based early warning	Developed drought forecast tool with dis- trict-level triggers, population impact overlays, and side-by-side forecast com- parisons; aligned with Early Action Proto- col.

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A co-creation framework was developed under I-CISK project, which was used to guide the co-creation process across the seven LLs (I-CISK, A prototype framework on co-creating end-user centred climate services, 2022). This framework consisted of different phases, from building continuous engagement, to co-delivering pre-operational CS innovation systems (Figure 2). This framework was applied in the LLs in a flexible, iterative, and context sensitive manner. The application of the co-creation approach was underpinned by a wide range of inputs (e.g., data, models, scientific and local knowledge) and activities (e.g., meetings, workshops, surveys), leading to outputs (e.g., pre-operation CSs) contributing to expected outcomes (e.g., enhanced capacity and awareness) and impacts (e.g., empowering of the stakeholders).

Figure 2: The co-creation process and its evaluation criteria to deliver user-centred climate services.

The methodology for monitoring and assessing the impacts of the I-CISK project has been developed through an iterative and participatory process, tailored to reflect the innovative nature of the project’s approach to co-creation and impact monitoring. The methodology was designed with two primary goals in mind: first, to systematically monitor and evaluate the expected impacts of the project, both for each LL and at the overall project level; and second, to develop and refine a ToC framework that is aligned with the co-creation processes central to I-CISK’s implementation strategy. This process also entailed the definition of KPIs connected to the ToC, providing measurable milestones for impact monitoring.

During the first part of the project (M1-18), we focused on designing an innovative, context specific, and systematic approach to impact assessment. After reviewing a range of existing ToC frameworks, we developed a novel ToC framework for I-CISK. What distinguished our approach from conventional ToC models was the deliberate integration of ToC elements with the phases of the co-creation process used in the I-CISK LLs (I-CISK, A prototype framework on co-creating end-user centred climate services, 2022). This alignment created a conceptual bridge between the theoretical underpinnings of impact pathways and the practical, participatory work being conducted in the LLs.

This framework was presented to and discussed with the consortium during the first General Assembly (September 2022 in Münster). Based on feedback received, we finalized a revised version of the ToC, which linked inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts to the key stages of co-creation in the LLs. The aim

was to enable systematic impact monitoring for each LL, while also ensuring that the impacts of the I-CISK project at large could be understood in relation to its co-creation framework.

While the innovative framework developed in the first period (M1–M18) offered a robust conceptual foundation, we encountered two main challenges in its implementation:

1. **Complexity and abstraction:** The framework, while innovative, remained relatively abstract, making it difficult for the LL teams to operationalize.
2. **Need for contextualization:** Each LL operated in distinct contexts, necessitating tailored ToCs to meaningfully guide monitoring and impact reflection.

In response to these challenges, during the second reporting period (M19–M36), we adapted and improved our approach. Recognizing the need for clarity and usability, we embarked on a simplification process, producing a new overarching I-CISK ToC diagram and narrative for the entire project, complemented by dedicated, customized ToC diagrams and narratives for each of the seven LLs. These LL-specific ToCs were developed as contextualised extensions of the overarching ToC, rooted in the same overall logic, but adapted to reflect the distinct settings, stakeholders, and dynamics of each Lab. This nested structure aligns with the approach described by (Davies R. , 2004) who emphasises the importance of representing complexity and scale in large, multi-level interventions. Rather than treating each ToC as an isolated plan, the LL ToCs function as grounded expressions of the broader theory, enabling us to trace change both locally and system-wide in a coherent and adaptive way.

The co-creation of the LL-specific ToCs and their refinement were structured as participatory and iterative processes:

- **Workshop:** A cross-learning workshop with all LL teams was held to guide the development of the tailored ToCs. This session introduced simplified templates and participatory techniques to facilitate co-creation of LL-specific ToCs.
- **Internal LL work:** Each LL team worked internally, drawing on their ongoing engagement with local stakeholders and their MAPs to draft their ToC narratives and diagrams.
- **Review and revision:** Draft ToCs were reviewed by the Task 1.3 team and iteratively refined through feedback sessions, including individual LL meetings and regular WP1 coordination meetings.
- **Validation:** LLs were encouraged to validate their ToCs with their respective MAPs, fostering ownership and enhancing relevance. Several LLs successfully completed this validation.
- **Finalization and communication:** The finalized project-wide ToC diagram and LL-specific diagrams were consolidated and are being disseminated through project materials, including a flyer that was published on the I-CISK website.

Another key component in our methodology was the structured alignment of KPIs with the ToC framework. The KPIs were selected and refined to reflect the expected impacts and objectives of the I-CISK project, including contributions to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and to the relevant EU/national policies, and impacts related to citizen engagement, knowledge co-production, resilience building, and the uptake of CSs.

Baseline values for KPIs were established in the first reporting period (M1–M18). During the second reporting period (M19–M36), progress was monitored, with attention to areas needing further work. A color-coded system (green/yellow/red) helped to visualize KPI performance and guide action planning. Additionally, impact stories were collected from the LLs to provide richer context and understanding of progress made, challenges faced, and lessons learned.

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3 Theory of Change frameworks for the I-CISK project

3.1 Overarching Theory of Change

The I-CISK ToC (Figure 3) depicts the trajectory of how the project will achieve its desired impact. It consists mainly of three spheres, i) sphere of control, ii) sphere of influence, and iii) sphere of interest. The sphere of control outlines the inputs required and activities needed to generate tangible outputs within the timeframe of the project. The sphere of influence depicts the outcomes of the project, which are the changes in society as a result of the project outputs being put into use in the short or longer term after the project has ended. Finally, the sphere of interest involves the overall impact of the project, these are the new conditions in society after the project outcomes have been achieved, and outputs are used effectively. The ToC rests upon various assumptions, some of which are tied to specific steps within it. Through the acknowledgement and testing of these assumptions, we can effectively manage risks, fine-tune strategies, and optimize the impact of the interventions.

3.1.1 Co-creation process

Within I-CISK, the sphere of control (inputs, activities, and outputs) is executed within the framework of co-creation (Figure 2) in LL environments (I-CISK seven LLs). This framework centres the needs of the users along the CS value chain and occurs through iterative engagements between various stakeholders on the value chain to produce CS that are not only useful and usable but also used.

3.1.2 Inputs

The inputs required for this include stakeholders on the CS value chain in the seven LLs that will be engaged in the process of generating tailored CS, including their decision processes and information needs. Additionally, both scientific and local data and knowledge will be required, in addition to technical resources and tools to facilitate the development of CS.

3.1.3 Activities

Activities in I-CISK will be directly linked to the co-creation process and will apply a range of approaches to engage stakeholders, such as serious gaming, workshops, and participatory modelling to name a few. Within this stage, stakeholders are engaged in the co-exploration of user needs, co-identification of adaptation strategies, co-development of climate data and knowledge, co-design, and co-evaluation of user-centred CS, and finally co-delivery of a user-centred CS.

Assumptions

For these activities to be undertaken, we assume that the stakeholders engaged in the process have the right skills and capacity to carry out the process.

3.1.4 Outputs

A key output for I-CISK is producing preoperational CS that can be used in the seven LLs. Several other products such as datasets and tools will also be developed, including guidance for the development of human-centred CS that enhances understanding of adaptation processes and centres the sustainable use of CS.

Assumptions

For the outputs to be produced, we assume that the co-creation process will be inclusive and time-managed, and that the data necessary for the development of CS is available.

3.1.5 Outcomes

Within the sphere of influence is our main outcome which is to inspire a change in society by having relevant society members make use of the various products curated and developed by I-CISK to not only further develop tailored and behaviourally informed CS, but to also enhance understanding of the adaptation options and capacity of users to use CS.

Assumptions

For the outcomes to be achieved, we assume that the CSs developed as part of I-CISK are tailored and fit for purpose to be understood by end users, as well as affordable.

3.1.6 Impacts

Within our sphere of interest is the overall impact, which is the improvement of society's resilience to the impacts of climate change, with users being well-informed to understand, process, and use climate information in decision-making.

Assumptions

For this to happen, we assume that the CSs produced are used, upscaled, and effective in supporting decision-making.

Assumptions:

1. Committed stakeholders with the right skills are involved in the living labs and consortium to carry out the process
2. The processes of co-creation in obtaining the inputs and through activities for this theory of change are inclusive and time managed
3. The data necessary for the development of climate service is available
4. The climate services developed are tailored and fit for purpose, and well understood by end users
5. The climate services produced are affordable
6. The climate service produced are used, upscaled and effective in supporting decision making

Figure 3: Overarching Theory of Change diagram for the ICISK project.

The diagram visualizes the project’s Inputs, Activities, Outputs, Outcomes, and Impacts. Inputs, Activities, and Outputs fall within the Sphere of Control: what the project team can directly manage and deliver. Outcomes and Impacts belong to the Sphere of Influence: areas where the project contributes to change, but results depend on external factors beyond direct control. For each activity, the selected approaches have been highlighted. Key assumptions have been identified and linked to specific steps in the Theory of Change; for example, Assumptions 4 and 5 must hold true for the Outcomes to be achieved after the Outputs are delivered.

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3.2 LL-tailored Theory of Change frameworks

Using the methodology outlined in the previous chapter, each LL developed its own tailored ToC, building on the overarching framework while reflecting the specificities of its local context.

3.2.1 Rijnland Delta, The Netherlands

The ToC diagram for the Rijnland LL is shown in Figure 4, with the corresponding narrative provided in the following paragraphs.

3.2.1.1 Inputs

The Rijnland LL concerns drought preparedness and adaptation in a water management district in the Netherlands. MAP members include representatives from the local water authority of Rijnland, water tourism sector representatives of boating clubs and members, and representatives of agricultural sector organisations and businesses. Their drought challenges, current hydrometeorological and drought monitoring information used, and user stories depicting potential drought mitigation decision processes and information needs, are key inputs. Next to the MAP members' inputs, local hydrometeorological data from monitoring stations, and seasonal hydrometeorological forecasts and climate change outlooks provided by I-CISK partners are used in the CS under development.

3.2.1.2 Activities

The activities for the co-development of the Rijnland drought CS evolve around workshops and bilateral meetings with the MAP members, for the co-requirements, co-design, and co-evaluation of the pilot drought awareness CS. In addition, sprint meetings between I-CISK project partners for iterative co-development of the CS are held. These interactions will continue up to the end of the project in October 2025, with two more rounds. One round of bilateral MAP sector group meetings to complete the co-creation process of the pilot CS application, and a final workshop with all MAP members to address sustaining and uptake of the CS beyond the project lifespan, e.g. through business models. One activity to foster up-scaling and exploitation beyond the MAP members, is to present at one of Rijnland's drought and climate change adaptation meeting(s).

Assumptions

For these activities to be undertaken, we assume that the stakeholders engaged in the process (MAP members) have the continued interest to invest time in meetings and workshops.

3.2.1.3 Outputs

The inputs and activities described above serve to result in a number of specific outputs. Most of the output components will together form a pre-operational Rijnland Drought forecasting and alert service with climate change impact information. The main components of the pilot CSs application are: 1) Seasonal streamflow forecast, 2) Seasonal Potential precipitation deficit forecast, 3) Weekly drought status and alert overview, and 4) Climate change impact information for Rijnland. The other outputs include presentations tailored for various potential next users, ranging from experts to business to students, and business model(s) for continuation and uptake of the Rijnland drought CS.

Assumptions

Here we assume that the co-creation process will be inclusive and time-managed, and that the data necessary for the development of the CS are available.

3.2.1.4 Outcomes

The outputs of LL Rijnland are designed to effectively contribute to the key outcomes envisaged from the beginning of the I-CISK project in consultation with the Rijnland water authority: 1) Increased preparedness for an upcoming drought event, through early awareness, to enhance operational coping by the MAP members in Rijnland, and 2) foster among the MAP members active awareness of, discussion on, and development of integrated long term drought mitigation strategies in a changing climate. For the co-developed drought CS to become and remain one of the vehicles in reaching these outcomes, it is an important outcome in itself that the service is used in MAP member decision making processes. Within the Rijnland area, the same CS can be scaled up to include more users and more user groups affected by droughts and the water authority's mitigation actions.

Assumptions

For this to happen, we assume that the products developed as part of I-CISK would be tailored and fit for purpose to be understood by end users, and also affordable.

3.2.1.5 Impacts

Ultimately the aim is to contribute to increased drought resilience in the Rijnland area and the Netherlands, in the short and the long term, through climate change adaptation by the MAP members and additional actors. As such, the impact is to be a reduction of damage and socio-economic adverse effects of droughts, in Rijnland specifically and the Netherlands as a whole.

Assumptions

Here, we make the assumption that the CS produced would be used, upscaled, and effective in supporting decision-making.

Assumptions

1. Committed stakeholders with the right skills are involved in the living labs and consortium to carry out the process
2. Consortium members have enough time available for technical development of the pre-operational CS
3. The processes of co-creation are inclusive and time managed
4. The climate services developed are tailored and fit for purpose, and well understood by end users
5. The data necessary for the development of climate services are available
6. The climate services produced are affordable also after 2 years after the end of the project
7. The data necessary for the development of climate services remain available for at least 2 years after the project
8. The climate services produced are used, upscaled and effective in supporting decision making
9. Drought challenges are critical for the MAP members and their sectors, now and in the future

Figure 4: Theory of Change diagram tailored to the Rijnland Living Lab.

Where appropriate, assumptions are linked to specific steps; other assumptions apply generally across the entire diagram.

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3.2.2 Andalucía, Spain

The ToC diagram for Spanish the LL is shown in Figure 5, with the corresponding narrative provided in the following paragraphs.

3.2.2.1 Inputs

The Spanish LL team of UCM and CREA identified a first set of key actors in Los Pedroches region at the design stage of the project. Once kicked off, the team amplified and adjusted the citizen groups, stakeholders, and decision-makers invited in the LL MAP and finally was able to engage a group of people representing relevant organisations. Actors engaged committed to the process formally and each engaged different professional profiles, in accordance with the LL dynamics and requests.

All MAP participants were asked what climate information they were currently using allowing the I-CISK team to identify gaps, needs, and expectations. Each of the participants shared what decision-making processes would benefit from improved information, thus also sharing challenges on climate change impacts. It is important to remark the LL was developed during a very intense drought episode and participants were highly interested in collaborating to improve their situation.

The LL allowed to share knowledge on existing tools and methods for developing CSs and could a) identify reasons why the current CS made available by local authorities were not so much known, b) propose innovative approaches for newly developed services from the international scientific arena, and c) treasure existing workflows, processes and initiatives by the MAP. Furthermore, it was possible to speak about technical aspects, such as preferred digital supports (smartphones), and limitations, such as internet access in rural areas.

Another important input to the setting of the LL is local knowledge, both on the climatic conditions of the past and present, biophysical specificities of the region (e.g. micro-climatic conditions) and the adaptation measures normally put in place. This allowed a solid basis for the further analysis and joint co-creation process, based on real experience-based knowledge and nurturing the overall, integrated initial diagnosis of the different aspects of vulnerability to climate change of the key sectors engaged.

The initial context setting also engaged MAP participants working with climate and environmental datasets, adding on possible synergies for further scientific advances and new project ideas, already from the start of the I-CISK project.

3.2.2.2 Activities

The Spanish LL setting allowed to co-explore social, behavioural and design factors influencing the adoption of CSs thanks to the elaboration of a solid co-creation framework (WP 1,2). Furthermore, it allowed the assessment of the human-climate feedback mechanisms at different spatial-temporal scale (WP 4). Assuming all input was correctly gathered from the MAP, this process allowed to generate experience-based knowledge to trace guidelines for co-designing next generation human centred CSs.

CS exploitation and dissemination, policy outreach, and capacity building (WP 6) activities allowed to strengthen capacity building on the matter, as well as reaching new target audiences to address the project results.

Co-implementation of the IT innovative cloud-based I-CISK web platform (WP 1,5) allowed to visualise the tailored climate information including local knowledge and scientific data (WP 1,2,3) developed by the LL co-creation process and deliver pre-operational CSs for use in the LL: Temperature and precipitation projections

and predictions, historical climate, hydrogeological characterization. These activities made need-based climate information available in a format and at a scale that is useful for end users.

Under the assumption that improved data quality allows integration and operationalisation of next generation CSs, gathering new scientific data indeed enabled to produce new datasets and actionable information products that integrate scientific and local knowledge (e.g., groundwater information, olive tree growth parameters).

The LL setting created spaces for communication with CS providers, purveyors, and end users, generating new relations between local actors. Furthermore, assuming no patent and other payments are further needed to exploit the system, a sustainability plan was developed to assure future availability of CS (WP 5), validating the added value to the new CS perceived by purveyors.

3.2.2.3 Outputs

Novel (empirical) models that provide insight on the human-climate feedback of adaptation options and actions were created as well as guidelines for co-designing next generation human centred CSs. The approach enabled new relationships to be established between key local actors within the LL and generate stronger community relationships.

The education material for capacity building developed to underpin the CSs and new actionable data embedded in it enabled correctly using the co-production framework by CS providers and purveyors to develop CSs, improving the users' knowledge and understanding about the impacts of climate change and adaptation options, and increase the exploitation of information and data from the Copernicus programme, the GEOSS and other global initiatives. The assumption that capacity building was effective and relevant target audiences were reached was confirmed.

Business models for sustainable operation and up-scaling of the next generation of CS enabled I-CISK data and tools are taken up and used by the EU CS market and beyond.

Pre-operational CSs for use in the LL: Temperature and precipitation projections and predictions, historical climate, hydrogeological characterization, integrating new datasets and actionable information products that integrate scientific and local knowledge (e.g., groundwater information, olive tree growth parameters) proved interesting enough to confirm the assumption that REDIAM (CS providers) will integrate the service into its website, make the services available after the end of the Project and these are used to inform the decision-making processes of LLs, also beyond the Project.

Indeed, CS purveyors see an added value to the new CS to improve need-based climate information made available in a format and at a scale that is useful for end users, allowing the CS providers and purveyors, including SMEs and sector organisations, improve their institutional and/or market position.

Assumptions

The outputs rely on the assumption that all input has been correctly gathered from the MAP, that data quality allows integration and operational use, and that the relationships built through the LL remain solid. It is also assumed that no patents or payments are needed to further exploit or scale the system.

3.2.2.4 Outcomes

Under the assumption a better relationship between stakeholders leads to a more resilient community, new relationships between key local actors within the LL, stronger community relationships and the successful

implementation of the co-production framework used by CS providers and purveyors to develop CS, enabled new opportunities for collaboration.

Enhanced users' knowledge and understanding about the impacts of climate change and adaptation options, uptake of I-CISK data and tools in relevant environments and the use of the pre-operational CSs to inform the decision-making processes allowed to empower citizens, decision-makers, and stakeholders to adapt their livelihoods and organisational activities to climate change both in the short and long term.

Thanks to the increased exploitation of information and data from the Copernicus programme, the GEOSS and other global initiatives, the use of this data to inform the decision-making processes of LLs, and perceived improvements of the market position of the economic sectors participating in the MAP, the impacts of climatic hazards on social, economic and environmental sectors are reduced.

Assumptions

The outcomes rely on the assumption that capacity-building activities were effective and reached the relevant target audiences. It is also assumed that REDIAM will integrate the CS into its website and keep it available beyond the end of the project. Finally, it is assumed that the CS proves useful for both providers and users.

3.2.2.5 Impacts

The Andalucía LL aspires to have the following impacts by the end of the I-CISK project:

1. The Analucia LL contributes to build cohesive and connected communities and acts as a project incubator, generating and taking advantage of new opportunities for collaboration. This impact is the result of the strong relationship built between local actors as a result of their collaboration in the LL, a trust that is resulting in further opportunities for collaboration, with actors participating jointly in proposals as well as generating new projects and seeking sources of funding to address identified challenges within the LL; for instance, water quality deterioration (UCM – CICAP collaboration), and soil management (HE Monalisa Project). These opportunities have arisen from the co-production process, the capacity building activities, dissemination, and policy outreach that are part of the ICISK process (WP1, WP2 and WP6 activities). Indeed, the LL setting enabling the participation of the map of local actors allowed building a framework for co-designing CS, the co-exploration of social, behavioural and design factors influencing the adoption of CS and the assessment of the human-climate feedback mechanisms at different spatial-temporal scale. The co-production framework is used by CS providers and purveyors to develop CS and underpins the assumption that improved relationships between the participants in the LL leads to more resilient communities, and that these novel models can actually provide insight on the human climate feedback of adaptation options and actors. The process delivered experience-based knowledge to guide the co-design of next generation human centered CSs, a valuable input for other, related projects in the area.
2. Citizens, decision makers, and stakeholders are empowered to adapt their livelihoods and organizational activities to climate change both in the short term and long term, thereby increasing their climate resilience. The climate information generated is useful thanks to the co-generation of knowledge and understanding of the impacts of climate change and of the needs to adapt to new conditions. Also, the climate information is improved (is needs-based) thanks to the co-identification of necessary climate information to underpin critical decisions in the region (olive farming, livestock rearing, forestry management) in a continuous feedback process integrating scientific and local knowledge. To support the co-creation process new databases and information are being generated

that relies partially on pre-existing databases (for instance Copernicus, local meteorological stations, other research projects -past and present- in the region). Under the assumption that the information provided is used and improves the decision-making process, local societies are empowered to adapt to changing conditions. This process is sustained by WP1, WP2 and WP3 activities.

3. Resilient region, communities, and farmers. The impacts of climatic hazards on social, economic, and environmental sectors are reduced: reduce drought vulnerability and became more drought resilient. The CS providers and purveyors, including SMEs and sector organizations, improve their institutional and/or market position thanks to the innovative information produced by the CS within ICISK. The ICISK co-creation process facilitates enriching existing tools and provides additional value to the use of climate data. Assuming the complementarity of CS produced provides an integrated view on risks and vulnerabilities, intersectoral dialogue fostered in the LL creates spaces for communication that improves their understanding of cross-sectoral impacts and thus help risk management. Sustainability of the developed CSs will depend on the economic and legal barriers to be overcome for data accessibility and continuity over time. This is linked to the work being developed under WP5.

Assumptions

The impacts assume that stronger relationships contribute to building a more resilient community. It is also assumed that the complementarity of the CSs produced offers an integrated view of risks and vulnerabilities, and that the information provided helps improve decision-making processes. Finally, it is assumed that stakeholders actively use the CSs to support their decisions.

Assumptions

1. All input was correctly gathered from the MAP
2. Data quality allows integration and operativization
3. Living lab relations are solid
4. No patent and other payments needed to further exploit the system
5. Capacity building was effective and relevant target audiences reached.
6. Redlam (CS providers) will integrate the service into its website and is available after the end of the project
7. The CS is useful for providers and users
8. Better relationship leads to a resilient community
9. The complementarity of CS produced provides an integrated view on risks and vulnerabilities
10. The information improves the decision-making process
11. Stakeholders use CS in the decision-making process

Figure 5: Theory of Change diagram tailored to the Spanish Living Lab.

Where appropriate, assumptions are linked to specific steps; other assumptions apply generally across the entire diagram.

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3.2.3 Emilia Romagna, Italy

The ToC diagram for the Emilia Romagna LL is shown in Figure 6, with the corresponding narrative provided in the following paragraphs.

3.2.3.1 Inputs

The application of the ToC to the Castellarano LL on the Secchia River focuses on enhancing water management amidst climate change. The initiative involves a variety of stakeholders, including the Regional Environmental Protection Agency (ARPAE), Regional Authority of Emilia-Romagna, local utilities and irrigation consortia, who provide the expertise, local data, and knowledge necessary for developing CSs and, in the case of consortia, also play a relevant role in water exploitation for agriculture. The context of this effort is shaped by the urgency created by climatic challenges such as the severe drought in 2022, highlighting the need for effective adaptation strategies to guarantee both environmental protection and a reasonable exploitation for agriculture and industry.

3.2.3.2 Activities

The project starts with the collection and integration of scientific and local knowledge, real-time gauging station data, and the experiences of past climatic events. This foundational data is crucial for informed decision-making and currently represents the main source of information to take operational decisions during drought. The core activities revolve around a co-creation process, where stakeholders engage in iterative workshops, focus groups, field trips, interviews, to develop an innovative CS. These activities aimed initially to identify local knowledge, and current decision processes, to be integrated with new scientific knowledge (forecast of incoming river discharge) and develop tailored climate information to boost new decisions. Through this process, a pre-operational CS is created, focusing on user-centered design that incorporates social and behavioral factors.

3.2.3.3 Outputs

The initiative expects several outputs, including building capacity in the stakeholders to leverage on seasonal/sub seasonal forecasts, instead of mere monitored values, to support drought management. Such CS may rely on local data to improve accuracy, but leverage on upstream existing (including but not limited to) open forecasts from Copernicus Emergency Management Service to enhance the understanding of climate adaptation processes. To provide such capability for that specific backend modules and a tailored Graphical user interface has been developed. Additionally, the prototyped solution shall be sustainable in the market and a business model has been sketched to provide robust elements towards sustainable operation and future commercial exploitation of this type of services.

Assumptions

Here we assume that users are confident enough in the potential of the new CSs to engage with and adopt them. The CSs produced are expected to be affordable, ensuring accessibility for intended users. It is also assumed that the value of these services can be reasonably estimated, for example by linking them to tangible resource gains or improved access to financing channels that support adoption. Finally, the necessary data for developing the CSs is assumed to be both available and operational.

3.2.3.4 Outcomes

The main outcomes of this initiative are aimed at changing societal behaviour towards more proactive water management, moving from actual "control "based near real time routine to more collaborative (and anticipated) decision making about drought management.

By integrating pre-operational CSs into regional resilience plans and emergency protocols, the project hopes indeed to promote from the regional government level downstream to users a shift from reactive to anticipatory decision-making in drought management. This includes enhancing the capacity of users to interpret and apply climate forecasts in their planning processes and promoting a collaborative approach to water resource management that leverages both free and paid forecasting services. Furthermore, optimization of strategies through the use of the CS shall give the core users like consortia the capability to access more flexible ecological flow regulations enhancing their capability to provide water in critical periods while keeping protection of the environ at first place.

Assumptions

It is assumed that pre-operational CSs can support “what-if” scenarios to foster more collaborative decision-making. The CSs produced are expected to be used, scalable, effective, and tailored to user needs, with end users able to understand and apply them. It is assumed that users can see real-world benefits over time, such as improved water availability during droughts through better management. Political willingness is expected to enable regulatory changes, for example, more flexible ecological flow rules for adopters. Further assumptions include that users are open to moving from old habits to new tools, no competing free public alternatives emerge, regional authorities back the process by promoting these services as best practices, and that the necessary data remains available and operational.

3.2.3.5 Impacts

The overarching impact sought by this initiative is to improve society’s resilience to climate change. This involves achieving a better balance between water availability for legitimate uses and reducing environmental stress, enabling well-informed decision-making that integrates both historical data and predictive CSs. The project aims to ensure that, beside the Lab application, the developed CS is scalable, effective, and potentially widely usable to support sustainable water management practices in other similar contexts (e.g. other relevant hydraulic nodes in the Region).

Assumptions

Here we assume that the initiative will support a shift toward more proactive and collaborative water management, moving beyond control-based, near-real-time routines. By integrating pre-operational CSs into regional plans and emergency protocols, it is assumed this will drive a transition from reactive to anticipatory drought management. Users are expected to build capacity to interpret and apply climate forecasts, combining free and paid services. Finally, we assume that using these services will help core users, like consortia, accessing tangible benefits like more flexible ecological flow regulations, balancing water provision during critical periods with environmental protection.

Assumptions

1. Committed stakeholders with the right skills are involved in the living labs and consortium to carry out the process
2. The processes of co-creation are inclusive and time managed
3. Users are confident enough about the potential of the new CS
4. The climate services produced are affordable
5. The value of the CS can be estimated reasonably, e.g. linked to tangible resources gain or availability to financing channels to foster adoption
6. The data necessary for the development of climate services are available and operational
7. The climate services produced are used, upscalable and effective in supporting decision making
8. Political willingness to move and change regulations accordingly, e.g., giving more flexible Ecological flow regulations for CS adopters
9. Pre-operational climate services can be used to support what if scenarios, this assumption is targeted to reach the outcome of more collaborative decision making

10. The climate services developed are tailored and fit for purpose, and well understood by end users
11. User of the CS shall be able to touch benefits in "real environment", e.g. check after a few years if expected improvements are achieved, for example if more water is available during drought than in the past years thanks to better management like preemptive storage or modular Ecological flow
12. Accepting to move from "hold habits" to new tools from users like Consortia for example
13. No other public funded ("free") alternative became available in the meanwhile
14. Regional Authority supports this process by including in its plans this type of CS among the "best practices"
15. The data necessary for the development and run of climate services are available and maintained operational
16. The climate change effect will not produce dramatic reductions of water availability beyond adaptation capacity
17. While CS is focused on better management enhancing availability of water for legitimate users, the users themselves shall do their part of the adaptation job, for example accepting a constructive discussion on changing water demand patterns (e.g. accepting also to contribute by crop changing)

Figure 6: Theory of Change diagram tailored to the Emilia Romagna Living Lab.

Where appropriate, assumptions are linked to specific steps; other assumptions apply generally across the entire diagram.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101037293

3.2.4 Erzsébetváros, Budapest, Hungary

The ToC diagram for the Budapest LL is shown in Figure 7, with the corresponding narrative provided in the following paragraphs.

3.2.4.1 Inputs

The Budapest LL did not start from scratch. Several committed partners worked behind the development of the CS, including experts (MAP members) from the local governments of Districts VI and VII who provided active assistance. These partners include the AirScan drone and IDEAS AI team, which creates meter-resolution heat maps from evening flights, as well as civil society organizations and volunteer residents who test the CityZcan sensor hub during street measurements. Decision-making processes particularly in need of heat information are organized around these actors, including the planning of green-blue adaptation measures, identifying hot spots, and raising public awareness. The technical backbone of the project includes developing high-resolution drone mosaics, CNN (Convolutional Neural Networks)-based temperature forecasting, a web-based Geographic Information System (GIS) dashboard, CityZcan microclimate sensors, and integrating the data. We have also developed an open-source web GIS stack, a PyTorch environment, and cloud servers. Adaptation is not just theory; the city already uses a national heat alert system, mist gates, private air conditioners, and a street tree program. The rich data assets—including orthophotos, thermal GeoTIFF mosaics, live CityZcan streams, and socioeconomic statistics—prove that Budapest has the necessary "raw materials" to accelerate heat adaptation. The task of the LL is to develop and combine these assets into a coherent, population-centered CS.

3.2.4.2 Activities

The LL's work proceeds in circular, user-centered cycles. Each step is refined based on the previous one's experiences. First, we determine how affected the locals are by the issue, what knowledge they have, and what behavioural triggers they have through online questionnaires and interviews.

As a result of evening drone measurements, we created centimetre-resolution land surface temperature (LST) mosaics and a data collection framework for CityZcan sensors. These revealed how certain street objects or land use increase the environmental heat load. This is accompanied by the creation of a co-design framework that incorporates social and behavioural psychological aspects. Residents, urban planners, and researchers jointly decide on analysis pilots, the service platform structure, and later, the serious game tool.

The results are made available to the public through a policy outreach and information portal. Drone images, interactive maps, and decision-support graphics will be presented online so that representatives, journalists, and residents can view the project's outputs and progress.

Meanwhile, Heat-insight apps (data visualization and processing scripts and downloadable CNN model) are being developed, and market research is exploring which business models would be best for making the service self-sustaining in the long term.

The system is based on a cloud-based GIS, where orthophotos, LST mosaics, CNN forecasts, and OpenStreetMap (OSM) layers run on the IDEAS server. This makes heat maps accessible from mobile phones or from an internet browser. Drone-generated "tile" mosaics fit together to provide high-resolution information on these heat maps.

Lastly, UX testing and gamification accompany all this: a cooperative board game is being developed to teach students and adults alike how to reduce or adapt to heat stress in their own streets and how to use CS service data to do so.

All activities follow proven live lab practices, such as rapid prototyping and incorporating real user feedback into the next development cycle. This approach strengthens the usability and social embeddedness of the CS step by step (city.zcan.eu/en/maps).

3.2.4.3 *Outputs*

The first tangible results of the LL activities are taking shape in the form of a comprehensive public engagement strategy. Thematic workshops, an open street exhibition, and targeted consultations ensure that service development ideas are shaped from the ground up. Educational and communication materials accompany the process. Short videos, eye-catching infographics, and animations based on drone footage make it easy to understand what the urban heat island effect is and how it is measured.

Visibility and scalability are increased through a scaling and gamification package, which includes open-source heat image analysis scripts and a cooperative board game in which players collaborate to cool the city.

Technically, the heart of the project is the CityZcan Sensor hub and real-time dashboard. The platform enables residents to measure temperature, humidity, Particulate Matter (PM) 2.5, and infrared values. The analytical toolkit and open data set — LST scripts — ensure the data is viewable, further developable, and reusable.

These products guarantee that the CS is not only "useful and usable," but also becomes an everyday tool for decision-makers, professionals, and residents.

Assumptions

In the output phase, the assumption is that critical data flows (repeated drone measurements and CityZcan sensor data) will remain uninterrupted. Risk management: We are working to ensure the service can operate sustainably after the project ends and that the necessary updates can be implemented.

3.2.4.4 *Outcomes*

The above outputs combine to form a needs-driven CS. Through continuous co-production, we provide a response to the urban heat island (UHI) problem in Budapest that district actors perceive as the most urgent. The resulting actionable UHI knowledge enables relevant, cost-effective interventions to be implemented.

The open code base and modular toolkit demonstrate EU-level interoperability, and any user can download and customize them.

This strengthens evidence-based urban planning. Urban planners and residents can see on a map where the greatest cooling potential lies. This enables them to target green and blue infrastructure development resources more effectively and optimize the geographical focus of cool roof subsidies.

These results are measurable in the short term and provide concrete decision support while establishing the knowledge and tools on which future social impacts can be built.

3.2.4.5 *Impacts*

Once the results are in, Budapest's heat resilience will be strengthened because CS will reveal hidden heat-related problems more effectively and make them locatable. Systems based on reliable data will stimulate a local CS market. Sensor installation, data analysis, and urban planning companies will receive new orders, and the city administration will be able to purchase services through transparent competition. This economic ecosystem can sustain and further develop the platform even after the project ends.

Meanwhile, citizens will play a role in decision-making. Measurements taken by CityZcan sensor volunteers will be published e.g. on the National Meteorological Service's open portal. Locals will be able to see how their data directly influences heatwave alerts and cool roof subsidy maps.

Economic savings will also be significant. Easily identifiable hotspots can optimize mitigation and adaptation measures. For example, they can reduce the energy consumption of air conditioners.

Finally, the online platform and cooperative board game raise climate awareness. Students, parents, and entrepreneurs learn together how to reduce the heat load in their street sections. Knowledge spreads within the community, involving a broad social base in implementing cooling measures.

These effects will permanently increase Budapest's ability to adapt to increasingly extreme heat waves caused by climate change, setting an example for other European cities on how to effectively combine science, technology, and community participation.

Assumptions

The assumption here is that the CS is effectively integrated into official decision-making processes. Risk management: We use communication tools to maximize the impact of the development.

Assumptions

1. Committed stakeholders with the right skills are involved in the living labs and consortium to carry out the process
2. The processes of co-creation are inclusive and time managed
3. The developed climate services (CS) will be adopted and further developed by local communities without obstacles and that users will understand the system's operation.
4. The climate services developed are tailored and fit for purpose, and well understood by end users
5. The climate services produced are affordable

6. Stakeholders (citizen groups, decision-makers, holders of local knowledge) will be capable of identifying and sharing relevant local and behavioural factors that influence climate adaptation.
7. The data necessary for the upscaling of climate services are available: high-resolution orthophotos, stitched thermal mosaics, CityZcan sensor streams, OSM layers and basic socio-economic statistics continue to flow to the IDEAS servers under open licences, with drone over-flight permits renewed each summer.
8. Heat-map layers are embedded in the district urban planning and heat alarm system and routinely cited in budget proposals; the open-source toolkit is packaged for rollout to other Budapest districts and Hungarian cities beyond the pilot area.

Figure 7: Theory of Change diagram tailored to the Budapest Living Lab.

Assumptions apply generally across the entire diagram.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101037293

3.2.5 Crete, Greece

The ToC diagram for the Crete LL is shown in Figure 8, with the corresponding narrative provided in the following paragraphs.

3.2.5.1 Inputs

The inputs required for this include stakeholders on the CS value chain that are engaged in the process of generating tailored CS, including their decision processes and information needs. The Crete LL attempts a multi-sectoral approach towards the tourism sector, incorporating stakeholders from main cross-cutting sectors in the island of Crete: Water management sector, Transportation sector (ports and roads), Accommodation sector, Academia sector, Business sector (knowledge purveyors and development companies) and an umbrella, governmental sector (part of ministry of tourism). Additionally, both scientific and local data and knowledge (e.g. historical measurements and data, decision thresholds, empirical processes, current workflows, assessments, and impact studies etc) are required, in addition to technical resources and tools to facilitate the development of CS.

3.2.5.2 Activities

Activities in I-CISK are directly linked to the co-creation process and apply a range of approaches to engage stakeholders such as workshops 1-2-1 videocalls, sharing of material and hands-on product testing. Within this stage, stakeholders are engaged in the: (a) co-exploration of user needs, where maturity over CS availability and potential as well as awareness over CC threats is built, (b) co-identification of adaptation strategies and co-development of climate data and knowledge through discussions and the implementation of a decision-timeline exercise, (c) co-design and co-evaluation of user-centred CS, based mainly on supported and free exploration of pre-operational CS and evaluation of interface as well as discussion on the collected feedback and its interpretation and finally (d) co-delivery of a user-centred CS, supplemented by the co-identification of the value proposition of the developed CS and the co-development of business story-lines to support preliminary potential for business development.

3.2.5.3 Outputs

A key output for I-CISK is producing preoperational CS that can be used in the LL. In the Crete LL, a series of services have been developed and are available in pre-operational phase, to support the tourism sector. These include in particular (a) a seasonal hydrological forecasting service for support of operational decision making in water management, (b) seasonal forecasts of tailored climatic indexes for tourism (accommodation sector), (c) seasonal forecasts of tailored climatic indexes for the transport sector (port services and road network) to support operational decision making, as well as (d) decadal projections of the above tailored products to support long-term planning and funding requests.

Several other products such as datasets and tools are also developed. These include:

- guidance for the development of human-centred CS that enhances understanding of adaptation processes and centres the sustainable use of CS,
- capacity building of stakeholders regarding awareness of CS availability and understanding the potential for decision making support and the options to incorporate CS information in existing workflows. This capacity building is necessary for achieving a similar level of maturity of the stakeholders at the above thematics, in order to ensure a uniform and efficient input at the phased of co-designing the CS,
- business storylines to identify preliminary potential for business development based on the next generation of CS, as well as a tiered approach – methodology for developing these storylines.

- new CS products such surface water flows for predefined period with estimates for more than 10 months ahead, seasonal forecasts of specific wind thresholds and directions, tailored climatic indexes for suitability of outdoor activities, landslide potential and others and
- new IT and scientific tools to support further use and exploitation of available Climate Data and related products.

Assumptions

Here we assume that the co-creation process will be inclusive and time-managed, and that the data necessary for the development of CS are available. Further, we assume that the development of business models will reach the level that is supported from the information and the type of CS produced, and that may not be the same for all CS products.

3.2.5.4 Outcomes

Within the sphere of influence is our main outcome which is to inspire a change in society by having relevant society members make use of the various products curated and developed by I-CISK to not only further develop tailored and behaviorally informed CS, but to also enhance understanding of the adaptation options and capacity of users to use CS. In this respect, we anticipate to support:

- an improved Water Management on the island of Crete which will ensure sufficient water availability for all uses during the summer, futuristic season (March- September) of peaking water demand, as well as under dry conditions, supporting the greater goal of water safety for the island and supporting achievement of the desired quality status of the water resources in the future,
- a better-informed planning and decision making (operational decisions for short-term planning, 1 to 4 months ahead) regarding port management of traffic and minimizing some of the maintenance costs. Additionally, an improvement of the long-term planning of protective works (10-20 years),
- an improved preparedness of the maintenance of road network, with regard to landslides-related damages,
- better informed decisions for maintenance works (during low touristic season) and outdoor activities (during high touristic season) planning in the tourism sector and
- an increase of the scientific capacity (viability, knowledge capacity) of the business sector (referring to “knowledge purveyors”) around the provision of down-streamed CS products.

Assumptions

For this to happen, we assume that the products developed as part of I-CISK would be tailored and fit for purpose to be understood by end users, and also affordable. Further, a basic assumption is that the developed CS produces value for each sector involved and that the value produced is enough to support incorporation of the new CSs in workflows.

3.2.5.5 Impacts

Within the sphere of interest is the overall impact which is the improvement of society's resilience to the impacts of climate change, with users being well-informed to understand, process, and use climate information in decision-making. Further, a specific to the Crete LL anticipated impact is that the Tourism sector will increase its climate resilience and viability, through the increase of climate resilience of the main, cross-cutting sectors (water, port, road network, touristic accommodation) which are empowered to adapt their livelihoods to climate change both in the short and long term. An additional impact is, through this process of CS development and new opportunities related to this development, the improvement of the institutional and

market position of relevant CS purveyors, including Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) and sector organizations.

Assumptions

Here, we make the assumption that the CS produced would be used, upscaled, and effective in supporting decision-making. For this to happen, we further assume that the value produced is enough to support the incorporation of the new CSs in workflows and that stakeholders' will to change the way they work and incorporate new workflows, which include new CS, is strong and persistent.

Assumptions

1. Committed stakeholders with the right skills are involved in the living labs and consortium to carry out the process
2. The processes of co-creation are inclusive and time managed
3. The data necessary for the development of climate services are available
4. The climate services developed are tailored and fit for purpose, and well understood by end users
5. The climate services produced are affordable
6. The climate services produced are used, upscaled and effective in supporting decision making
7. Stakeholders trust climate service (are included in decision making)

8. The development of business models will reach the level that is supported from the information and the type of CS produced, and that may not be the same for all CS products
9. CS produces value for each sector involved
10. The value produced is enough to support incorporation of the new CSs in workflows
11. The CS produces value for each sector involved
12. The value produced is enough to support incorporation of the new CSs in workflows
13. Stakeholders' will to change the way they work and incorporate new workflows which include new CS is strong and persistent

Figure 8: Theory of Change diagram tailored to the Crete Living Lab.

Where appropriate, assumptions are linked to specific steps; other assumptions apply generally across the entire diagram.

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3.2.6 Alazani river basin, Georgia

The ToC diagram for the Alazani LL is shown in Figure 9, with the corresponding narrative provided in the following paragraphs.

3.2.6.1 *Inputs*

Climate services, hydromet and meteorological services, in Georgia are still in their early stages of development. Tailored services are only available to specific sectors and stakeholders, such as government organisations, energy companies, etc. With that in mind, the MAP was set up to include key organisations (National Environment Agency, under the Ministry of Environment and Protected Areas) mandated to provide weather and climate information in the country. The MAP also included service providers like the irrigation authority (Georgian Amelioration), the Rural Development Agency, and local representatives (like Kakheti Regional Administration, Information Consultation Center, Kakheti Regional Development Foundation, Georgian Farmers Association, and local NGOs). In addition to including key stakeholders, we identified synergies with other ongoing projects – for example, the Multi-Hazard Early Warning Systems project by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) – and strategic gaps that may exist which I-CISK could leverage. Developing CS to support drought risk management is a key priority for Georgia in the Alazani-lori basin, thereby defining the larger context within which the I-CISK project will operate.

3.2.6.2 *Activities*

Effective CS require a participatory and inclusive approach to ensure they meet the needs of diverse stakeholders. Within the I-CISK project, this is enabled through the implementation of a co-creation approach. The co-creation framework lays the foundation for CS, which is user-centred and contextually relevant. The framework incorporates social and behavioural factors to ensure the services are tailored to the needs and capacities of local communities. Another key activity in the case of the Georgian LL is outreach and capacity building to ensure that the project and the topic of CS are accessible to all members of the MAP. Targeted outreach and engagement activities foster an understanding of CS and its benefits, equipping stakeholders with the knowledge to integrate them into their decision-making processes. This step strengthens the demand for CS and enhances their perceived value. Following capacity-building sessions, the interactions with the MAP closely follow the steps outlined in the co-creation framework. Iteratively, the MAP members are engaged in ideation and co-exploration to capture the knowledge, priorities, and decision-making processes of local communities and relevant stakeholders. Participatory methods (focus group discussions, interviews, problem tree analysis, decision timelines, etc) are used to engage stakeholders and solicit their input. This allows CS development to be informed by the local context as much as possible and aligned with existing practices and challenges. Following that, stakeholders also collaborate to design and test a pre-operational CS interface and visualisation tools. This iterative process allows for feedback and refinements, ensuring that the services are user-friendly, intuitive, and meet the specific needs of different user groups. Evaluation mechanisms are embedded to assess the effectiveness and usability of the CS before full-scale implementation. To maximise impact, options for sustaining and scaling CS are continually explored. This includes identifying institutional support mechanisms and policy integration opportunities. In the case of the Georgian LL, sustainability opportunities are explored with the National Environmental Agency (NEA), the Rural Development Agency (RDA) and Georgian Amelioration. Planning for long-term sustainability is crucial for broader applicability; CS can be expanded to reach more users and continue providing valuable insights for climate-informed decision-making.

3.2.6.3 *Outputs*

One of the key outputs of the I-CISK project is a framework of co-creation guidelines to inform the design of next-generation CS. These guidelines encapsulate best practices for co-designing human-centered CS. On an

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LL level, interventions associated with capacity building led to improved awareness and understanding of CS and its application among end users. This enhanced knowledge helped foster confidence in integrating CS into policy, planning, and operational decision-making. The use of participatory methods, like decision timelines, enabled a deeper understanding of decision-making processes and user-specific risks and needs. Pathways for sustainability were explored to ensure the long-term viability and scalability of CS. In the Georgian LL, this meant engaging with key institutional stakeholders to understand the enabling environment for CS in Georgia and processes (water allocation, rural development and drought and emergency management) that the planned CS can support.

Assumptions

The realisation of these outputs hinges on certain key assumptions that were made to ensure the feasibility of the co-creation process and prevent stakeholder fatigue. This includes the fact that the planned capacity-building activities are sufficient to alleviate the accessibility issues. Secondly, all data collection efforts successfully capture the full scale of information, and the co-creation process leads to effective mediation of the goals and interests of different CS users such that the pre-operational CS is viewed as legitimate by all members of the MAP.

3.2.6.4 Outcomes

Implementing the I-CISK project in the Alazani-Iori LL can lead to several key outcomes that drive meaningful change in how CS is conceptualised and designed, their role in decision-making and the use of climate data to empower citizens to cope and adapt. One of the project's key outcomes is the broader adoption of the co-creation methodology developed by I-CISK in future CS projects by CS providers to design and implement effective, user-centred CS. This ensures that CS remains participatory, responsive, and aligned with local needs. Furthermore, the pre-operational CS developed by I-CISK are adopted by national stakeholders to inform their workflows and are disseminated even beyond the project's lifespan. Moreover, the developed drought-related CS are effectively integrated into decision-making at multiple levels, including farmer livelihoods and irrigation authorities within the LL. Users engaged in these processes also gain a deeper understanding of climate change impacts and available adaptation options. These outcomes extend beyond the project, raising awareness among stakeholders and fostering long-term resilience and informed adaptation planning. On a national level, engagement with I-CISK projects and its partners also leads to greater exploitation of data and information from international climate monitoring programs such as the Copernicus Programme and the Global Earth Observation System of Systems (GEOSS), as well as other global initiatives.

Assumptions

Again, achieving these outcomes depends on key conditions being met that are assumed during the project implementation. For instance, the broader adoption of the co-creation framework within the LL depends on whether the framework is culturally sensitive and endorsed by local stakeholders and if local stakeholders have sufficient resources to implement such a process meaningfully. Similarly, wider adoption of drought-related CS and exploitation of climate data and information relies on whether CS developed by I-CISK is perceived as salient to the needs of end users and whether national entities have sufficient technical capacity and resources to make pre-operational services operational. Finally, the use of CS for decision-making by different end-user groups (within and outside the Alazani-Iori basin) depends on the scaling up of CS and the capacity of CS providers and purveyors to sensitise members of the local community about CS and its use.

3.2.6.5 Impacts

The successful implementation and scaling of CS lead to significant long-term impacts, strengthening local and national capacities to adapt to drought and water scarcity. These impacts build climate resilience, ensure informed decision-making, and integrate CS into policy and practice. With this in mind, the overarching aim of the Alazani-lori LL was to create awareness about the CS and its use among the key stakeholders in the basin (e.g., winemakers, cereal farmers, etc). As a result of increased awareness and access to CS, farmers are better equipped to adapt their livelihoods to challenges involving drought and water scarcity. With improved understanding and actionable information, stakeholders can make informed decisions on water management, crop selection, and adaptive farming techniques. At a broader scale, integrating CS into national drought management policies enhances institutional capacity to respond to climate risks. Governments and relevant agencies are better prepared to develop data-driven strategies, implement early warning systems, and establish long-term drought mitigation plans. This contributes to a more coordinated and effective response to drought conditions, improving national resilience to climate change.

Assumptions

Several assumptions have been made when projecting these impacts. First, it is assumed that the developed CS will be effectively scaled out to farmer groups beyond those initially involved in the project. This broader dissemination is critical to ensuring widespread benefits across different agricultural communities. Additionally, strengthening national capacity relies on the assumption that CS developed within the project are successfully embedded into national drought management policies and instruments. This requires institutional buy-in, policy alignment, and sustained engagement with governmental and regulatory bodies. Without these conditions, CS' long-term integration and sustainability may be limited.

Assumptions

1. The capacity building interventions are enough to create awareness about CS among MAP members
2. Data collection efforts sufficiently capture relevant local knowledge and information about decision making process
3. The goals and interests of different users represented in the MAP were sufficiently mediated
4. Co-creation framework is accepted by national and local actors as an approach to develop CS
5. National and local actors have sufficient resource to implement co-creation framework
6. CS developed is sufficiently salient to the needs of different users
7. There is sufficient technical capacity to move from pre-operational CS to operational CS
8. Workshops are accessible to stakeholders
9. The project has sufficiently built capacity of CS providers, purveyors and users
10. CS developed is sufficiently embedded in the workflow of the NEA and is regularly disseminated and communicated with other ministries and organisations (sectoral information providers and purveyors)
11. CS developed is scaled out to farmers groups in the region (beyond those represented in the MAP)
12. CS developed is sufficiently embedded in the workflow of the NEA and is regularly disseminated and communicated with other ministries and organisations (sectoral information providers and purveyors)
13. CS developed within I-CISK is sufficiently embedded in the national drought management policies and instruments

Figure 9: Theory of Change diagram tailored to the Alazani Living Lab.

Where appropriate, assumptions are linked to specific steps; other assumptions apply generally across the entire diagram.

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3.2.7 Southern Lowlands Districts, Lesotho

The ToC diagram for the Lesotho LL is shown in Figure 10, with the corresponding narrative provided in the following paragraphs.

3.2.7.1 Inputs

The inputs of the Lesotho LL include key stakeholders such as the Lesotho Red Cross Society (LRCS), Lesotho Meteorological Services (LMS), and the Disaster Management Agency (DMA). The decision processes in place focus on Early Action Protocols for droughts and cold waves, detailing the characteristics of the adaptation process to these hazards within the framework of Anticipatory Action. The work draws on existing data, including forecast products from LMS, drought forecasts from SMHI, and cold-wave forecasts from ECMWF, as well as scientific and local knowledge. The way of working is grounded in the procedures of the Red Cross Red Crescent Movement and a locally led engagement approach that strengthens the capacity of LMS, DMA, and LRCS.

3.2.7.2 Activities

The main activities involve assessing the forecasting skills of both global and national climate products, developing and implementing guidelines and workshops for CS development, and undertaking business development to ensure sustainability beyond the project's lifespan. The team also focuses on co-identifying local knowledge through in-country data collection, establishing an initial framework for co-designing CSs that integrates social and behavioural insights, and co-designing and co-evaluating pre-operational CS interfaces and visualisations. A central part of the work is the co-implementation of the Impact Based Forecasting portal.

3.2.7.3 Outputs

The project aims at delivering improved trigger models, providing training and support to LMS, DMA, and LRCS to strengthen their capacity for CS development, and establishing a business model that ensures the sustainability of the Impact Based Forecasting platform. The key output is the Impact Based Forecasting portal (Climate Service) for droughts to support Anticipatory Action, as well as new datasets and actionable information that integrate both scientific and local knowledge in the LL.

Assumptions

These outputs rely on certain assumptions: that LMS, DMA, and LRCS are fully engaged and actively participating, that the necessary data for CS development is available and can be integrated effectively, and that local knowledge research is well designed and representative of the communities involved.

3.2.7.4 Outcomes

The expected outcomes of the project include the updating of Early Action Protocols with the improved trigger models in the long term, as well as enhanced capacity within LMS, DMA, and LRCS for CS development. The Impact Based Forecasting portal is expected to be used by LRCS to inform timely decision-making processes. The project also aims to empower communities with access to climate services that blend scientific insights with indigenous knowledge for better understanding. Beyond the project, I-CISK data and tools are expected to be taken up and used by the EU's Copernicus programme and other global initiatives.

Assumptions

Achieving these outcomes depends on assumptions such as the CS being fit for purpose because it is based on local context and needs, data being open and shared, clear links between science and local knowledge, and sufficient capacity and coordination within LRCS.

3.2.7.5 *Impacts*

The impacts foreseen include a reduction in the impacts of drought on people living in the Southern Lowlands Districts and the Senqu Valley, reaching approximately 27,000 people, and a reduction in the impact of cold waves on people living in the Leboneng corridor, Thaba-Putsoa, Maluti, and the Drakensberg corridor, reaching around 20,000 people.

Assumptions

These impacts may not be fully achieved if certain assumptions are not satisfied. Regional authorities should recognise and promote the CSs as best practices and LRCS should have sufficient access to communities and maintain their trust over the long term. Additionally, funding for response should be available when needed.

Assumptions

1. LRCS staff, with the right skills, are actively involved in the living labs and consortium and take ownership of the process and its outcomes
2. DMA and LMS are actively involved in the living labs and consortium
3. Improvements are available and effective
4. Guidelines and workshops are based on actual needs and context appropriate
5. The data necessary for the development of climate services are available and can be seamlessly integrated into a platform through automated processes
6. Local knowledge research is well designed and a representative sample of the communities is reached
7. All stakeholders agree to update the protocol
8. All stakeholders are engaged
9. The Red Cross Red Crescent Movement has capacity to coordinate
10. The portal developed is based on local context and needs and thereby fit for purpose
11. The connection between scientific and local knowledge is clear and readily comprehensible
12. Data can be openly shared
13. LRCS EAP cold wave is in place
14. LRCS EAP drought is in place
15. Funding for response is available
16. There is sufficient staff available at LRCS
17. LRCS improves weak coordination, info flow and ways to communicate to villages
18. LRCS has sufficient access to communities
19. LRCS is accepted/ trusted by communities

Figure 10: Theory of Change diagram tailored to the Lesotho Living Lab.

Where appropriate, assumptions are linked to specific steps; other assumptions apply generally across the entire diagram.

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4 Impact monitoring and assessment

4.1 Key Performance Indicators

To support the monitoring and evaluation of the I-CISK project, several KPIs have been defined. While these indicators provide target outcomes for the full project, these are also actively monitored throughout the project to ensure project activities remain on track. Monitoring and evaluation of these KPIs is an integral part of the ToC framework. Annex-1 provides an overview of the KPI's and their status at the end of the first reporting period. Additionally, and as an innovative aspect of this project, we linked specific KPIs to key steps in the co-creation process. This allows us to monitor the quality and effectiveness of the process itself. This relationship is illustrated in Figure 11 in Annex-1.

Note that these KPIs are categorised in the following way: S-# refers to KPIs relevant to Stakeholder engagement, O-# to overall implementation, D-# to dissemination and E-# to exploitation. The table colour codes the progress of the KPIs for convenience, where green rows refer to KPIs that are well on course; Yellow rows refer to KPIs needs attention; Red rows refer to KPIs that require additional attention. Grey rows refer to KPIs not relevant to the reporting period.

Moreover, each KPI is linked with the ToC component (input, activities, outputs, outcomes, and impacts), which facilitates a structured monitoring and evaluation. Table 2 provides the status of the impact-related KPIs; for a full assessment of all the KPIs, please see Annex-1.

Table 2: An overview of the impact-related KPIs and their status as per M45, July 2025.

KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Means of verification
D-9	Number of impact stories demonstrated in the LL attributed to the project implementation (at least one per LL)	>7	Each of the seven LLs has developed at least one impact and business story.	This report; (Ziogas, Tzimas, van Anandel, & al., 2025)
E-2	Number of SMEs improving their market position	3	Three SMEs (GECOSISTEMA, 52North and Ideas Science) are part of the project consortium. The work carried out under I-CISK project has contributed to enhance the market position of these SMEs. This is demonstrated by successful acquisition of projects, increase/sustaining of staff and gains in reputation.	I-CISK EU portal; (Ziogas, Tzimas, van Anandel, & al., 2025); SMEs company profiles/websites

KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Means of verification
E-3	New jobs creation in full-time equivalents (FTE) for skilled employees within 3 years after the project	>10	Expected after the project closure. The target is expected to be achieved, considering the strengthened market position of the I-CISK partners. For example, a few partners (e.g., SMEs-52 North and GECO-sistema) has successfully acquired projects building on the I-CISK experience and networks. Other partners have enhanced their visibility and reputation, which will contribute to increased business gains leading to job creation.	I-CISK EU portal; (Ziogas, Tzimas, van Anel, & al., 2025); SMEs company profiles/websites
E-4	Number of business stories developed, and unique value propositions of CS identified for upscaling (min 1 for each LL)	>7	Each of the seven LLs has developed at least one impact and business story. In each case business analysis and upscaling potential is examined, which demonstrate potential	This report; (Ziogas, Tzimas, van Anel, & al., 2025)
E-6	Number of users (e.g. citizens, end users, decision-makers, business sectors) using new CS proposed in the I-CISK to make better-informed climate adaptation decisions, to increase resilience to multiple risks and multiple sectors in EU regions and beyond	>50	Fifteen CS are co-created under I-CISK project. The I-CISK web-based platform is launched (see I-CISK website) where most of these CSs are available. The users (within and beyond I-CISK LLs) can benefit from these CS. There are over 150 users representing about 50 organizations, participating in the MAPs; at least most of these users are expected to use new CS co-developed under I-CISK project.	Minutes of WP1 meetings; (Masih, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2022); (Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024); (Pesquer, Pechlivanidis, & al., 2024); (Bagli, Mazzoli, & al., 2024); (Egan, Emerton, & al., 2025); I-CISK web-based platform; I-CISK website

4.2 Impact stories

The LLs created under this project have generated a variety of impacts, some directly tied to the development and use of CSs, and others reflecting broader changes in practices, relationships, and personal growth. These stories capture moments where the work of the LL has inspired new local decisions, shifted the way stakeholders engage with climate resilience, or opened up opportunities for early career researchers.

Rather than focusing solely on technical achievements, the impact stories highlight how people, communities, and organisations have been affected, sharing both successes and the challenges encountered along the way.

Each story reflects a journey, with its own starting point, turning moments, and outcomes. Together, they offer insights into how the LLs are helping to build knowledge, foster trust, and support better decisions in the face of climate risks.

Story 1: Improved forest conservation thanks to co-created Climate Services in the Cardeña Montoro Natural Park

Living Lab: Los Pedroches (Spain)

Situation: what was the status quo?

The Cardeña Montoro (C-M) Natural Park managers evaluate the areas needing reforestation, calculate the quantity and species required, and request a plant nursery to grow those plants so they can be planted in June the following year. Pedro, the park manager, analyses the health of the forest and introduces new plants to help the ecosystem recover from drought and plagues.

Complication: what changed or created a problem?

Unpredicted climate impacts, such as persistent drought and plagues, increase forest decay during the year. This situation makes it difficult to calibrate the plants requested with actual reforestation needs that arise after one year, and to estimate the survival rates of young plants. Pedro observes strong forest decay and struggles with young plants drying out due to changing climate conditions and the increasing presence of pests like the Processionaria (*Thaumetopoea pityocampa*).

Question: what question or need arose?

The C-M Natural Park managers need to calibrate the plants requested one year in advance with actual reforestation needs and planting conditions that arise after one year. Pedro asks himself: “How many plants will I need to restore next planting season?”

Answer: what happened to address the situation?

C-M Natural Park managers shared their challenges within the I-CISK LL and participated in co-creating a CS that predicts seasonal conditions, such as rainfall in June and consecutive days with temperatures above 32 degrees Celsius. This information helps estimate survival rates of new plantations and expected forest decay. Pedro contributed to creating this CS to better evaluate the number of trees required to restore the forest.

Story 2: Integration of heterogeneous data sources

Working package: WP5

Situation: what was the status quo?

Data sets have been openly available in separate, mostly expert-targeted data sources.

Complication: what changed or created a problem?

Finding, assessing, and integrating these disparate data sets has been cumbersome and challenging.

Question: what question or need arose?

There was a need to combine different data sets into a single application.

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Answer: what happened to address the situation?

A common framework based on open standards and a data ingestor were developed, enabling seamless combination of data sources into a single application. This provided end users with a rich, integrated information product, greatly simplifying access and usability.

Story 3: Bringing Climate Services to the Alazani-Iori

Living Lab: Alazani (Georgia)

Situation: what was the status quo?

The Kakheti region, part of the Alazani-Iori basin in Georgia, is highly important for agriculture, with a long tradition of cultivating grapes, cereals, and vegetables. Most families depend on agriculture for their livelihood.

Complication: what changed or created a problem?

Despite being extremely fertile, the region faces many challenges due to climate change and environmental degradation. Each year the region faces impacts arising from floods or droughts or hail. These conditions have led to farming becoming extremely challenging and unproductive in the region.

Question: what question or need arose?

Farmers can no longer rely solely on local knowledge to plan agricultural activities. There is a need for anticipatory measures to minimize losses and make better-informed decisions. For example, farmers decide whether to plant wheat or maize based on estimated precipitation, but erratic rainfall patterns complicate these choices and cause economic losses.

Answer: what happened to address the situation?

A new CS with reliable seasonal forecasts (temperature, precipitation, droughts) will help farmers to inform their crop choices and better plan their farming activities.

Story 4: Enhancing decision making in water management under increasing frequency of climatic extremes

Living Lab: Crete (Greece)

Situation: what was the status quo?

Water management in Crete, a large Mediterranean island, is challenging due to its climate and precipitation patterns. Every year, the water manager allocates water permits among different users such as farmers and municipalities, based on historical precipitation records and past experience.

Complication: what changed or created a problem?

Climate change pressures, a booming tourist sector that more than doubles the island's population during dry summer months, and increased environmental demands complicate water allocation. Consecutive dry years and drought exacerbate these challenges.

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Question: what question or need arose?

What can the water manager do to allocate water in spring (March or April) to ensure summer demands are met while avoiding overuse that might jeopardize water reserves under changing climate conditions? How can the water manager better estimate if the upcoming year will be dry or wet, and ensure the safety of water reserves without compromising economic activities such as tourism and agriculture?

Answer: what happened to address the situation?

The water manager was introduced to seasonal climatic services tailored to address these specific management questions, supporting operational decision making. After testing the services ahead of a third consecutive dry year, the water manager recognized their full potential and is interested in incorporating them into regular water management practices.

Story 5: Seasonal decision making in the transportation sector

Living Lab: Crete (Greece)

Situation: what was the status quo?

Ports and associated marinas serve as vital gateways to Crete. Effective management of port traffic and development is essential for the island's broader economic sector. The port manager makes short-term decisions about port traffic, typically on a day-to-day or two-to-three-days-ahead basis. Storm damage often requires unavoidable maintenance work.

Complication: what changed or created a problem?

Climate change and the flourishing tourism sector, which doubles the population during the high season lasting up to seven months, put significant pressure on port traffic reallocation. Increased climatic variability, with more frequent extremes such as winds, surges, and heat events, further strain traffic management and increase maintenance costs. Decisions rely on short-term forecasts and experience, limiting planning.

Question: what question or need arose?

How can the port manager better guide port traffic in advance to avoid extreme weather impacts and reduce the need to redirect large vessels to other ports, thus avoiding economic losses? How can port traffic management, especially of large vessels, be better planned to prevent damage to floating platforms during extreme wind events?

Answer: what happened to address the situation?

The port manager became informed about seasonal climatic services that can address these specific questions and support operational decision making. Awareness has grown that decision making can be supported over much longer periods (seasonal forecasts), enabling better planning and reducing economic losses.

Story 6: From reaction to anticipation: transforming drought management in Emilia-Romagna

Living Lab: Emilia-Romagna (Italy)

Situation: what was the status quo?

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Water allocation decisions by relevant players such as irrigation consortia hydropower producers in Emilia-Romagna relied primarily on historical records and real-time monitoring of river flows. Operational restrictions to protect minimum ecological flows were reactive, often implemented only after critical thresholds were breached, creating tension between environmental protection and legitimate users' needs during droughts.

Complication: what changed or created a problem?

With the increasing frequency and severity of drought events, stakeholders recognised that reactive measures were no longer sufficient to ensure water availability for agriculture while safeguarding river ecosystems. The severe drought in 2022 highlighted the limitations of current planning approaches, as decisions could not be anticipated in time and shared in terms of responsibility among users and the regulating authorities, to reduce economic and environmental impacts.

Question: what question or need arose?

How can water managers anticipate drought impacts earlier to plan storage, optimise distribution, and implement operational restrictions and mitigation measures proactively, ensuring both environmental protection and water availability for relevant usages?

Answer: what happened to address the situation?

Through the I-CISK LL, regional authorities and agencies together with main users co-designed a CS providing sub-seasonal and seasonal hydrological forecasts for strategic hydraulic nodes like Castellano. This service enables users to explore “what-if” scenarios, communicate early warnings to final users like farmers, and adjust withdrawals before reaching critical thresholds. The approach promotes a shift from reactive control-based decisions to anticipatory and collaborative drought management. Discussions with the Region are ongoing to integrate forecast-based operational rules into Water Protection Plans and Resilience Plans, fostering governance innovations that reduce bureaucratic delays during emergencies and enhance society's resilience to climate change.

Story 7: Empowering climate risk intelligence: how I-CISK boosted GECOsistema's capabilities

Company: GECOsistema

Situation: what was the status quo?

Before joining the I-CISK project, GECOsistema was already working in the field of environmental consulting and urban planning, offering services related to flood risk mapping, climate adaptation, and nature-based solutions. However, our approach to climate risk intelligence was largely driven by static models, limited stakeholder engagement, and fragmented data sources. Although we were supporting local authorities with technical analyses, our tools lacked the dynamic, co-creation-based elements needed to integrate CSs directly into decision-making processes. The company was seeking ways to evolve from being a data provider to a strategic partner in climate resilience, but we lacked access to broader European networks, advanced methodologies for co-producing services, and scalable digital tools to engage end users more effectively.

Complication: what changed or created a problem?

As climate impacts intensified and urban stakeholders demanded more actionable insights, it became clear that our existing tools and workflows were no longer sufficient. Clients began requesting more user-driven,

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site-specific CSs that could evolve with changing risks and planning needs. At the same time, competition was growing, especially from tech-savvy startups and international players integrating AI, satellite data, and participatory approaches into their CSs. GECOsistema faced a strategic challenge: how to shift from traditional consulting to a more agile, co-designed, and intelligence-driven model. We needed to upskill our team, adopt new methodologies, and embed users directly into the development process—something we had limited experience with at scale.

Question: what question or need arose?

We began asking ourselves: How can we make our climate risk services more dynamic, co-created, and tailored to the real needs of local decision-makers? What tools, skills, and partnerships do we need to move beyond static assessments and deliver climate intelligence that supports ongoing adaptation and planning? More specifically, we needed to understand how to integrate local knowledge, improve user engagement, and deliver services that are both scientifically robust and operationally useful for municipalities, regional agencies, and other end-users.

Answer: what happened to address the situation?

Through our involvement in the I-CISK project, GECOsistema was able to rethink its approach to CSs, actively engaging in co-design processes with end users across multiple LLs. We collaborated with researchers, municipalities, and local stakeholders to develop climate risk tools that were more interactive, user-centric, and grounded in real decision-making contexts. The project exposed our team to innovative methodologies for transdisciplinary co-creation, integration of Earth Observation data, and climate scenario communication. As a result, we strengthened our technical and strategic capabilities, enhanced our service portfolio, and broadened our network across Europe, positioning GECOsistema as a more agile and credible player in the climate intelligence space.

5 Measures to maximise the impact of the project: communication and dissemination

I-CISK has developed a communication and dissemination strategy during the first reporting period. In general, the implementation results are very promising in reaching out to the identified stakeholders using various means of communication and dissemination. For example, the I-CISK website and social media channels have contributed to share the project information and results with over 5000 people across the world. The I-CISK team members have participated in a number national and international events; these events have high relevance for science, policy, and practices arenas. Nine Journal articles are published. Three policy briefs are produced. Such activities contribute to maximize the I-CISK impacts in the EU regions and beyond. More details on communication and dissemination related activities are provided in the respective KPIs listed in Table 3; more information can be found at the I-CISK website.

Table 3: Communication and dissemination related KPIs and their status.

KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Means of verification
D-10	Number of events organized to share the (impact and business) stories from the demonstrator CS beyond the LL (at least one per LL country)	>7	All the LLs are in the process of organizing final events to demonstrate pre-operation CS as well as share the experiences and resources emerging from the I-CISK project. The primary target groups are the MAP members in most cases as LLs are considered the main market for the co-created CS. However, participation beyond MAP members is also expected.	Minutes I-CISK General Assembly 2025 Meeting. I-CISK social media (website and LinkedIn)
D-11	Number of presentations made to disseminate I-CISK results at science-policy (side) events	>4	>10 (e.g., EU GDSO Policy Event, March 2023; I-CISK side event at UNESCO Conference as well as presentation of results on stakeholder engagement in another session); WB DRR conference in Japan; Drought resilience +10 conference in Geneva; EGU 2024; Waternet Conference 2024); European Climate Change Adaptation (ECCA) conference 2025 (brokerage event; special session co-organized with other projects).	(Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024), I-CISK Newsletters, social media (website and LinkedIn), conference proceedings
D-1	Number of visitors to project website	>3000	The I-CISK website has already attracted more than target users (e.g., crossed over 5000 marks in M36-October 2024).	(Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024);

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Means of verification
				I-CISK website analytics
D-2	Number social media (Twitter, LinkedIn) followers	>300	>300: Twitter (>100), Linked in (>200). Linked in is more actively used than Twitter. Regular posts are made on LinkedIn, which receives reasonably good coverage.	(Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024); I-CISK website analytics; I-CISK social media (twitter and LinkedIn profiles)
D-3	Number of science-policy briefs disseminated	3	Three science-policy-practice briefs are generated and disseminated. One policy brief is produced, and dissemination started with drought resilience +10 workshop. The recommendations are included in the conference declaration; a good outcome leading to impact on policy change (e.g., the conference declaration provides important input to UNCCD COP16). Two other policy briefs were launched at the ECCA 2025 conference; one of these briefs was jointly developed with the three sister projects, LOCALIZED, REACHOUT and RE-THINKACTION, funded under the same call as of I-CISK.	I-CISK policy briefs (I-CISK, Policy Brief #1: Crossing the last mile in climate services: Putting policies into action (Joint policy brief with the LOCALISED, RethinkAction and REACHOUT projects, 2025; I-CISK, Policy Brief #2: Activating global climate data through co-creating local climate services: Early warning systems used by all, 2025; I-CISK, Policy Brief #3: Translating Climate Services Policies into Actions: Recommendations from Seven Living Labs in Europe and Africa, 2025); I-CISK newsletter and social media (website and LinkedIn)

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Means of verification
D-4	Number of publications on CS in non-scientific sectoral magazines/periodicals & general media	5	Well on course. One publication by CENN during first reporting period. During the second reporting period several blog posts and news items were placed, including one publication in a major national newspaper (El País, Spain), as well as in local and sectoral publications. A few business sector publications are planned for 2025.	Specific media outlets; I-CISK website; (Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024)
D-5	Number of scientific publications in peer-reviewed scientific literature	>15	11 Journal articles published; a few more are under review/preparation.	The references with weblinks are provided at the I-CISK website
D-6	Number of educational CS videos produced and available online	>4	Well on course: one Video is produced from the Spanish LL (Nikole's work on groundwater. Four mini-documentary videos are under development, which will feature I-CISK work in four LLs (Spain, Lesotho, and Georgia and Hungary). Concept is finalized, production process under way.	I-CISK website
D-7	Number of attendees from public and private CS sector to I-CISK online course (MOOC)	>50	Not applicable in M1-M45; expected in year after July 2025 when MOOC will be launched.	IHE Delft Open Courseware Platform (enrolment statistics)
D-8	Number of attendees from public and private CS sector at I-CISK CS brokering events	>30	One brokerage event was organized during ECCA 2025 conference held in Rimini Italy. Additionally, several side events, were organized (which are more than originally planned) at international conferences (e.g., UNESCO conference and Waternet Symposium held in 2024).	I-CISK social media (website and LinkedIn); conference proceedings/programme
D-12	Number of citizens, end users and decision-makers made aware of the next generation of CS in the LL and beyond	>5000	The ongoing communication and dissemination efforts contribute towards this KPI, which show outreach to much higher than target numbers (e.g., when considering website visits, LinkedIn post impressions, conference presentations, journal publications, newsletter distributions).	(Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024); I-CISK newsletters and social media (website and LinkedIn)

KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Means of verification
D-9	Number of impact stories demonstrated in the LL attributed to the project implementation (at least one per LL)	>7	Each of the seven LLs has developed at least one impact and business story.	This report; (Ziogas, Tzimas, van Anandel, & al., 2025)

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6 Discussion and conclusion

The ToC has played a central role in guiding the I-CISK project's approach to impact planning, monitoring, and evaluation. As a structured framework, the ToC helps clarify how and why desired changes are expected to occur by mapping pathways from inputs and activities to outputs, outcomes, and longer-term impacts. An essential part of clarifying the ToC is the deliberate effort by LL actors to identify and articulate the (often) implicit assumptions that underpin their change pathways. This process requires intentional reflection and facilitated dialogue to uncover, articulate, and critically examine these underlying assumptions.

Developing a comprehensive and meaningful ToC, however, requires time, resources, and conceptual clarity, particularly for teams less familiar with this approach. In the early stages of I-CISK, the project developed an overarching ToC framework to provide coherence across diverse LL contexts. However, given competing priorities and time constraints, the development of LL-specific ToCs occurred later in the project than initially intended. Ideally, ToCs should be co-created as early as possible in a project lifecycle to guide design and implementation from the beginning. However, too early on is also not possible as a certain level of clarity about the outputs (e.g. CS in case of I-CISK) to be co-created has to be crystallized. In terms of the co-creation framework, the co-explore and co-identify steps have to be accomplished as much as possible. During the second reporting period of I-CISK, significant efforts were made to simplify and contextualize the ToC process, ensuring it was accessible and practically useful for all partners. Through participatory workshops, internal teamwork, and iterative review processes, each LL developed a tailored ToC that reflects its specific context, priorities, and stakeholder dynamics. This co-creation process proved instrumental in transforming the ToC from a conceptual framework into a practical tool that supports strategic thinking and effective project implementation.

The participatory nature of ToC development also fostered ownership among LL teams and their stakeholders, increasing the framework's relevance and usability. When developed collaboratively and in a user-friendly manner, ToCs become intuitive and highly valuable, not only as planning tools but also as instruments for reflection and correction. Validation of the ToC assumptions has so far focused primarily on the links between project activities and immediate outputs. In several LLs, these assumptions were effectively confirmed, contributing to the successful delivery of planned outputs. However, many assumptions related to longer-term outcomes and systemic impacts remain to be tested, and these will require further assessment over time, even beyond the project timeframe. Final conclusions on project impact can therefore only be drawn through continued monitoring and evaluation until the end of the project and, in some cases, beyond its formal conclusion.

The integration of KPIs with the ToC framework has further strengthened the project's capacity for impact monitoring. Regular assessment of KPIs, supported by a traffic-light system to identify areas of progress and concern, has proven useful in guiding implementation and informing decisions. Qualitative impact stories, collected alongside quantitative indicators, have enriched this evidence base by capturing emerging changes in user behaviour, institutional uptake, and community resilience.

In conclusion, the ToC process in I-CISK has evolved into a valuable asset for both strategic planning and adaptive management. While the delayed timing of LL-specific ToC development presented initial challenges, the participatory and iterative refinement process ultimately enhanced the utility and ownership of the framework. As the project progresses, the continued validation of impact assumptions and close alignment with KPIs will be essential for understanding and demonstrating the value of co-created CSs in diverse local contexts. The novel framework and experience from I-CISK on integrating ToC approach, co-creation process

and KPIs into a project lifecycle can provide valuable insights to advance the ToC framework and its innovative application for outcomes and impact focused project design and implementation.

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8 Annexes

8.1 Annex-1: An overview of the KPIs, links to the Theory of Change components and co-creation process and their status by M45 (July 2025).

Table 4: An overview of the KPIs and their status as per M45, July 2025

KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
O-1	Number of decision processes requiring tailored climate information identified within the specific contexts of the LL (at least 2 decision processes per LL)	>14	The seven LLs of I-CISK have at least 2 decision making processes requiring tailored climate information identified within their specific contexts.	Input	WP1 & WP2	(Masih, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2022); (Moschini, Emerton, & al, 2022); (Van den Homberg, Rastogi, & al., 2024); (Egan, Emerton, & al., 2025)
O-2	Number of climate adaptation options and climate actions co-identified (at least 3 options and actions per LL)	>21	The seven LLs of I-CISK have at least 3 or more climate adaptation options and climate actions co-identified.	Input	WP2	(De Stefano, Ropero Szymańska, & al., 2023); (Van den Homberg, Rastogi, & al., 2024)
O-4	Number of multi-model climate forecasting systems from existing services and datasets (Copernicus, EMODnet, GE-OSS) co-identified to meet user needs in each LL	>3	Prediction systems from different providers (e.g., ECMWF SEAS5, E-HYPE/WWH and CMCC SPS) were assessed for the I-CISK LL. There are also local/regional models per LL as well (e.g., SARCOF model for Lesotho).	Input	WP3	(Du, Clemenzi, & Pechlivanidis, Hydrological regimes explain the seasonal predictability of streamflow extremes, 2023); (Pechlivanidis, Du, & Clemenzi, 2024); (Pesquer, Pechlivanidis, & al., 2024); (Du & Pechlivanidis, Hybrid approaches enhance

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
						hydrological model usability for local streamflow prediction, 2025)
S-4	Number of end users involved in participatory modelling and serious gaming to investigate the linkages and feedback between climate change and adaptation actions (at least 10 per LL)	>70	A number of participatory modelling activities (e.g., co-development of system archetypes and decision-tree timelines) and two serious games have been used to engage end users within I-CISK but also more broadly beyond the project.	Input	WP4	(Muller, Biella, & al., 2023); (Biella, Wamucii, & al., 2024); (Bela, Muller, & al., 2025); (Rastogi, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2025); I-CISK social media (website and LinkedIn)
S-5	Number of citizens, decision makers and stakeholders involved in the demonstration of pre-operational CS (at least 10 per LL)	>70	Over 150 different actors are participating in the co-creation process. The final sets of pre-operational CSs are ready and are publicly available at the I-CISK website. The demonstrations are in progress/planned across the LLs.	Input	WP1 & WP5	(Masih, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2022); (Bagli, Mazzoli, & al., 2024); (Ziogas, Tzimas, van Andel, & al., 2025); I-CISK social media (website and LinkedIn); attendance lists/minutes (meetings & workshops in the LLs)

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
S-6	Number of citizen groups, stakeholders and decision makers in LL collaborating in co-production of CS (at least 3 per LL)	>21	>21; All LLs have at least 3 stakeholder groups representing the MAP. Most of these groups actively participated in the co-creation process, though with variable degree of involvement across the LLs.	Input	WP1	(Masih, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2022); List of MAP members
S-8	Number of citizens, stakeholders and decision-makers participating in the events organized to share the (impact and business) stories from the demonstrator CS beyond the LL (at least 50 per LL)	>350	The impact and business story lines are developed for each LL. The exploitation strategies are under development. The LLs are in the process of organizing final events where MAP members (primary focus group) and other stakeholders will be presented with the CS. Additionally, CS and potential business and exploitation aspects are showcased during international events (e.g., ECCA 2025 conference).	Input	WP1 & WP5	(Masih, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2022); (Bagli, Mazzoli, & al., 2024); (Ziogas, Tzimas, van Aniel, & al., 2025); I-CISK social media (website and LinkedIn); attendance lists/minutes (meetings & workshops in the LLs)

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
O-5	Number of climate prediction models analysed	25	Five climate prediction systems/models examined in detail (ECMWF SEAS5, CMCC SPS, E-HYPE/WWH, GEOSS; Copernicus and EDO). About 10 others were briefly reviewed (e.g., Drought monitor CSIC; WMO services such as GDPFS; Coupled Model Inter-comparing Project (CMIP with example of six models).	Activity	WP3	(Du, Clemenzi, & Pechlivanidis, Hydrological regimes explain the seasonal predictability of streamflow extremes, 2023); (Pechlivanidis, Du, & Clemenzi, 2024); (Pesquer, Pechlivanidis, & al., 2024); (Du & Pechlivanidis, Hybrid approaches enhance hydrological model usability for local streamflow prediction, 2025)
O-6	Number of tailored CS variables and indicators evaluated from a user-oriented perspective	>5	As part of co-creation process user centred evaluations were conducted for the pre-operational CS co-designed under I-CISK. The target is fully met, as each of the seven LLs has more than one variable and indicator used in the evaluations.	Activity	WP3, WP5 & WP1	(Baugh, Egan, & al., 2025); (Egan, Emerton, & al., 2025); (Van Andel, Mazzoleni, & al., 2025)
O-8	Number of participatory modelling and serious gaming actions carried out with CS end-users (at least 2 per LL)	>14	A number of participatory modelling activities (e.g., co-development of system archetypes and decision-tree timelines) and two serious games have been used to engage end users within I-CISK	Activity	WP4	(Muller, Biella, & al., 2023); (Biella, Wamucii, & al., 2024); (Bela, Muller, & al., 2025); (Rastogi, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2025); I-CISK social media (website and LinkedIn)

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
			but also more broadly beyond the project.			
O-9	Number of human-climate feedback processes quantitatively assessed	5	Multiple archetypes were identified including Fixes-that-fail, Drifting goals, Band-aid solutions, and Success to the successful. Couple of them were assessed in detail for the selected LLs.	Activity	WP4	(Muller, Biella, & al., 2023); (Biella, Wamucii, & al., 2024)
O-14	Number of the LL CS co-design roadmaps defined	7	A generic roadmap document developed for all LL labs. All LL tailored it for their use. The roadmaps are living documents and are being implemented and revised as needed.	Activity	WP1	(Werner, Masih, & al., Roadmap for the collaboration between the Living Labs (WP1) and Work Packages 2-6, 2023a); LL roadmaps
S-3	Number of participatory activities (e.g. meetings, workshops, focus group discussions, interviews) held to co-explore end-user needs, knowledge, adaptation needs and behaviour (>5 per LL)	>35 WP1 WP2	Overall, more than 75 meetings were held in all the seven LL. These meetings include bilateral discussions, group meetings with different stakeholders, MAP meetings etc. Meetings are often held online (especially during first year due to COVID) as well as face to face. Generally, each LL have held more than 10 meetings during M1-M45.	Activity	WP1 & WP2	I-CISK periodic review reports (Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 1: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M1-M18 (November 2021-April 2023), 2023b; Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
						Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024); (De Stefano, Ropero Szymańska, & al., 2023); (Rastogi, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2025)
S-7	Number of co-production workshops held in LL (at least 5 per LL)	>35	30 workshops with MAPs (at least 3 in each LL) until M45 in addition to several bilateral meetings with the key actors.	Activity	WP1	I-CISK periodic review reports (Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 1: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M1-M18 (November 2021-April 2023), 2023b; Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024); (De Stefano, Ropero Szymańska, & al., 2023); (Rastogi, Van

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
						Cauwenbergh, & al., 2025)
D-10	Number of events organized to share the (impact and business) stories from the demonstrator CS beyond the LL (at least one per LL country)	>7	All the LLs are in the process of organizing final events to demonstrate pre-operation CS as well as share the experiences and resources emerging from the I-CISK project. The primary target groups are the MAP members in most cases as LLs are considered the main market for the co-created CS. However, participation beyond MAP members is also expected.	Activity	WP1 & WP5	Minutes I-CISK General Assembly 2025 Meeting. I-CISK social media (website and LinkedIn)
D-11	Number of presentations made to disseminate I-CISK results at science-policy (side) events	>4	>10 (e.g., EU GDSO Policy Event, March 2023; I-CISK side event at UNESCO Conference as well as presentation of results on stakeholder engagement in another session); WB DRR conference in Japan; Drought resilience +10 conference in Geneva; EGU 2024; Waternet Conference 2024); ECCA conference 2025 (brokerage event; special session co-organized with other projects).	Activity	All	(Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024), I-CISK Newsletters, social media (website and LinkedIn), conference proceedings

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
O-3	The guidelines for co-designing next-generation human-centred CS are finalized and made public	1	Draft guidelines are available and are used/further developed within I-CISK, the manual has been published on the ICISK website. The final guidelines are in the process of development and will be completed and launched within the project time-frame-work.	Activity	WP2	I-CISK MS10 document; Co-creation flyer; I-CISK co-creation guideline online version (under preparation)
O-7	Number of new datasets and actionable information products generated by integrating local information with large scale climate information (at least one per LL)	>7	The pre-operational CSs (>7) combine local data (in some cases local knowledge as well) with large scale climate information in all the LLs. More details are available at the I-CISK web-based platform hosting the co-created CS.	Activity	WP3 & WP5	(Van den Homberg, Rastogi, & al., 2024) (Bagli, Mazzoli, & al., 2024); (Pesquer, Pechlivanidis, & al., 2024); (Rastogi, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2025)
O-10	Number of novel (empirical) models developed to provide insight on the human-climate feedback of adaptation options and actions	5	Multiple archetypes were identified including Fixes-that-fail, Drifting goals, Band-aid solutions, and Success to the successful. The conceptual models were developed for the seven LLs. Two archetypes were assessed in detail for the selected LLs including model development.	Output	WP4	(Muller, Biella, & al., 2023); (Biella, Wamucii, & al., 2024)

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
O-11	Number of next generation pre-operational CS co-designed and demonstrated in the LL (at least one per LL)	>7	Fifteen CSs are co-designed in the seven LLs. The I-CISK-web based platform features most of these CS. The demonstrations of these CS are in progress/planned.	Output	WP1, WP3 & WP5	Minutes of WP1 and I-CISK general assembly meetings; (Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024); (Bagli, Mazzoli, & al., 2024); (Pesquer, Pechlivanidis, & al., 2024)
O-12	Number of business models developed to upscale the next generation of CS (at least one per LL)	>7	The business model storylines for the sustainable exploitation of CS are developed by each of the seven LLs. This work builds on a four-tiered analytical framework, emphasizing a bottom-up approach that starts from specific use cases and expands to potential broader market applications within and/or beyond the LLs.	Output	WP5	(Ziogas, Tzimas, van Anandel, & al., 2025)

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
O-13	Number of open-source tools, front, and back end, integrated to Copernicus and GEOSS, and adaptable to create new CS	>5	A number of (>5) open-source options have been identified and integrated into I-CISK CS platform. For example, a Climate Data Ingestor is developed to handle the ingestion and transformation of data from multiple sources, including Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS), SMHI, and ERA5 datasets. Another key achievement is the successful development and release of the I-CISK platform codebase on GitHub.	Output	WP5	(Bagli, Mazzoli, & al., 2024); I-CISK web-based platform; GitHub (https://github.com/icisk).
O-15	Number of pre-operational CS launched (at least one per LL)	>7	Fifteen pre-operational CS are co-created under the I-CISK project. The I-CISK web-based platform is launched that features most of these CS (see I-CISK website)	Output	WP1, WP3 & WP5	Minutes of WP1 meetings; (Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024); (Pesquer, Pechlivanidis, & al., 2024); (Bagli, Mazzoli, & al., 2024); I-CISK web-based platform; I-CISK website
D-1	Number of visitors to project website	>3000	The I-CISK website has already attracted more than target users (e.g., crossed over 5000 marks in M36-October 2024).	Output	WP6	(Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
						Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024); I-CISK website analytics
D-2	Number social media (Twitter, LinkedIn) followers	>300	>300: Twitter (>100), Linked in (>200). Linked in is more actively used than Twitter. Regular posts are made on LinkedIn, which receives reasonably good coverage.	Output	WP6	(Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024); I-CISK website analytics; I-CISK social media (twitter and LinkedIn profiles)

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
D-3	Number of science-policy briefs disseminated	3	Three science-policy-practice briefs are generated and disseminated. One policy brief is produced, and dissemination started with drought resilience +10 workshop. The recommendations are included in the conference declaration; a good outcome leading to impact on policy change (e.g., the conference declaration provides important input to UNCCD COP16). Two other policy briefs were launched at the ECCA 2025 conference; one of these briefs was jointly developed with the three sister projects, LOCALIZED, REACHOUT and RETHINKACTION, funded under the same call as of I-CISK.	Output	WP6	I-CISK policy briefs (I-CISK, Policy Brief #1: Crossing the last mile in climate services: Putting policies into action (Joint policy brief with the LOCALISED, RethinkAction and REACHOUT projects, 2025; I-CISK, Policy Brief #2: Activating global climate data through co-creating local climate services: Early warning systems used by all, 2025; I-CISK, Policy Brief #3: Translating Climate Services Policies into Actions: Recommendations from Seven Living Labs in Europe and Africa, 2025); I-CISK newsletter and social media (website and LinkedIn)

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
D-4	Number of publications on CS in non-scientific sectoral magazines/periodicals & general media	5	Well on course. One publication by CENN during first reporting period. During the second reporting period several blog posts and news items were placed, including one publication in a major national newspaper (El País, Spain), as well as in local and sectoral publications. A few business sector publications are planned for 2025.	Output	WP6	Specific media outlets; I-CISK website; (Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023–October 2024), 2024)
D-5	Number of scientific publications in peer-reviewed scientific literature	>15	11 Journal articles published; a few more are under review/preparation.	Output	All	The references with web-links are provided at the I-CISK website
D-6	Number of educational CS videos produced and available online	>4	Well on course: one Video is produced from the Spanish LL (Nikole's work on groundwater. Four mini-documentary videos are under development, which will feature I-CISK work in four LLs (Spain, Lesotho, and Georgia and Hungary). Concept is finalized, production process under way.	Output	ALL	I-CISK website
S-1	Gender Balance in stakeholder representation and participatory research in LL (Percentage Women)	~50%	Reasonably good gender balance is achieved across the LLs, except one where MAP members from the stakeholder groups are mostly represented by males due to lower proportion of women representatives in general.	Outcome	WP1	(Masih, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2022)

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
O-16	Change in the use of CS in the LLs compared to baseline in particular understanding of CS use barriers and incentives	Increase	Availability and use of CS is assessed for each LL. In general, MAP members are now better aware of the available CS including the barriers and incentives (e.g., accuracy, communication, science-policy gaps, coordination, and financing). The work is in progress to evaluate use cases. The assessment shows that the CS prototypes hold substantial promise in supporting decision-making processes.	Outcome	WP1 & WP2	(Masih, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2022); (Moschini, Emerton, & al, 2022); (Van den Homberg, Rastogi, & al., 2024); (Egan, Emerton, & al., 2025)
S-2	Number of decision-making processes of stakeholders demonstrably changed due to the outcomes and improved capacities on climate information from the project	>5	The decision-making processes are identified. The assessment shows that CS prototypes hold substantial promise in supporting both immediate operational choices (e.g. responding to imminent drought or heatwaves) and longer-term adaptation strategies (like urban greening or integrated water-resource planning).	Outcome	WP1 & WP2	(Masih, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2022); (Moschini, Emerton, & al, 2022); (Van den Homberg, Rastogi, & al., 2024); (Egan, Emerton, & al., 2025)
D-7	Number of attendees from public and private CS sector to I-CISK online course (MOOC)	>50	Not applicable in M1-M45; expected in year after July 2025 when MOOC will be launched.	Outcome	WP6	IHE Delft Open Courseware Platform (enrolment statistics)

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
D-8	Number of attendees from public and private CS sector at I-CISK CS brokering events	>30	One brokerage event was organized during ECCA 2025 conference held in Rimini Italy. Additionally, several side events, were organized (which are more than originally planned) at international conferences (e.g., UNESCO conference and Waternet Symposium held in 2024).	Outcome	WP6	I-CISK social media (website and LinkedIn); conference proceedings/programme
D-12	Number of citizens, end users and decision-makers made aware of the next generation of CS in the LL and beyond	>5000	The ongoing communication and dissemination efforts contribute towards this KPI, which show outreach to much higher than target numbers (e.g., when considering website visits, LinkedIn post impressions, conference presentations, journal publications, newsletter distributions).	Outcome	WP6	(Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024); I-CISK newsletters and social media (website and LinkedIn)
E-1	Number of market segments targeted	7	The business model storylines for the sustainable exploitation of CS are developed by each of the seven LLs. The market segments fall within the boundaries of the LLs (five cases) as well as beyond (two cases).	Outcome	WP5 & WP6	(Ziogas, Tzimas, van Anandel, & al., 2025)
E-5	Co-production framework adopted beyond the project (at least one per country of the LL)	>7	The co-creation framework is widely communicated and disseminated. The guidelines are under development and will be	Outcome	WP2 & WP6	I-CISK deliverables D2.8 and D2.9

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
			made public. These efforts are expected to promote the use within and beyond the project.			
D-9	Number of impact stories demonstrated in the LL attributed to the project implementation (at least one per LL)	>7	Each of the seven LLs has developed at least one impact and business story.	Impact	WP1, WP5 & WP6	This report; (Ziogas, Tzimas, van Andel, & al., 2025)
E-2	Number of SMEs improving their market position	3	Three SMEs (GECOSISTEMA, 52North and Ideas Science) are part of the project consortium. The work carried out under I-CISK project has contributed to enhance the market position of these SMEs. This is demonstrated by successful acquisition of projects, increase/sustaining of staff and gains in reputation.	Impact	WP5	I-CISK EU portal; (Ziogas, Tzimas, van Andel, & al., 2025); SMEs company profiles/websites
E-3	New jobs creation in full-time equivalents (FTE) for skilled employees within 3 years after the project	>10	Expected after the project closure. The target is expected to be achieved, considering the strengthened market position of the I-CISK partners. For example, a few partners (e.g., SMEs-52 North and GECOsistema) has successfully acquired projects building on the I-CISK experience and networks. Other partners have enhanced their visibility and reputation, which will contribute to	Impact	WP5	I-CISK EU portal; (Ziogas, Tzimas, van Andel, & al., 2025); SMEs company profiles/websites

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KPI #	KPI Description	Target	Status M45 (July 2025)	Link to ToC components	Link to I-CISK WP	Means of verification
			increased business gains leading to job creation.			
E-4	Number of business stories developed, and unique value propositions of CS identified for upscaling (min 1 for each LL)	>7	Each of the seven LLs has developed at least one impact and business story. In each case business analysis and upscaling potential is examined, which demonstrate potential	Impact	WP5	This report; (Ziogas, Tzimas, van Anandel, & al., 2025)
E-6	Number of users (e.g. citizens, end users, decision-makers, business sectors) using new CS proposed in the I-CISK to make better-informed climate adaptation decisions, to increase resilience to multiple risks and multiple sectors in EU regions and beyond	>50	Fifteen CS are co-created under I-CISK project. The I-CISK web-based platform is launched (see I-CISK website) where most of these CSs are available. The users (within and beyond I-CISK LLs) can benefit from these CS. There are over 150 users representing about 50 organizations, participating in the MAPs; at least most of these users are expected to use new CS co-developed under I-CISK project.	Impact	All	Minutes of WP1 meetings; (Masih, Van Cauwenbergh, & al., 2022); (Werner, Masih, & al., Periodic Report 2: Innovating Climate Services Through Integrating Scientific and Local Knowledge Progress Period: M19-M36 (May 2023-October 2024), 2024); (Pesquer, Pechlivanidis, & al., 2024); (Bagli, Mazzoli, & al., 2024); (Egan, Emerton, & al., 2025); I-CISK web-based platform; I-CISK website

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Figure 11: Framework that integrates Theory of Change elements and KPIs with co-creation process.

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8.2 Annex 2: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
ARPAE	Regional Environmental Protection Agency (Emilia Romagna Living Lab)
CNN	Convolutional Neural Networks
COP	Conference of the Parties
CS	Climate Service
DMA	Disaster Management Agency in Lesotho (Lesotho Living Lab)
ECCA	European Climate Change Adaptation (Conference)
EOBS	ENSEMBLES daily gridded Observational dataset for Europe
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
GFA	Georgian Farmers' Association (Alazani Living Lab)
GIS	Geographic Information System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KRDF	Kakheti Regional Development Foundation (Alazani Living Lab)
LMS	Lesotho Meteorological Services (Lesotho Living Lab)
LRCS	Lesotho Red Cross Society (Lesotho Living Lab)
LST	Land Surface Temperature
LL	Living Lab
MAP	Multi-Actor Platform
NEA	National Environmental Agency (Alazani Living Lab)
OSM	OpenStreetMap
PM	Particulate Matter
RDA	Rural Development Agency (Alazani Living Lab)
REDIAM	Environmental Information Network of Andalusia (Spanish Living Lab)
RER	Regional Authority of Emilia-Romagna (Emilia Romagna Living Lab)
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
ToC	Theory of Change
UHI	Urban Heat Island

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UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
WP	Working Package

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I-CISK

HUMAN CENTRED CLIMATE SERVICES

Colophon:

This report has been prepared by the H2020 Research Project “Innovating Climate services through Integrating Scientific and local Knowledge (I-CISK)”. This research project is a part of the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Framework Programme call, “Building a low-carbon, climate resilient future: Research and innovation in support of the European Green Deal (H2020-LC-GD-2020)”, and has been developed in response to the call topic “Developing end-user products and services for all stakeholders and citizens supporting climate adaptation and mitigation (LC-GD-9-2-2020)”. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101037293.

This four-year project started November 1st, 2021, and is coordinated by IHE Delft Institute for Water Education. For additional information, please contact: Micha Werner (m.werner@un-ihe.org) or visit the project website at www.icisk.eu

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